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CoSeC grand challenges. Revised edition

D Jones, S Longshaw, A Oliver, et.al.

February 2026

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**Computational Science Centre
for Research Communities**

Grand Challenges

February 2026

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Introduction

The [Computational Science Centre for Research Communities](#) (CoSeC) is a national Centre delivered by UKRI's Science and Technology Facilities Council ([STFC](#)). It sits within STFC's [Scientific Computing](#) department, where it draws from a large and diverse team of expert Research Technical Professionals.

As a Centre for the collaborative development, support and maintenance of key research software, CoSeC provides a sustained and consistent mechanism to deliver the software needed by UKRI's research communities. Its mission is to *deliver research software as an infrastructure* which it achieves through long-term strategic relationships with organised communities across UKRI's research landscape.

The [CoSeC community](#) consists of Collaborative Computational Projects ([CCPs](#)) and High-End Computing Consortia ([HECs](#)), as well as [six new communities](#) funded in 2024 to enable community scoping to identify and define viable new communities for the future.

In 2025 CoSeC began to explore the Grand Challenges that are facing our communities over the next 10 years. The purpose of this exercise was to identify a set of high-level challenges relevant for computational research across UKRI and to produce a set of guiding statements that encompass the aims and objectives of [UKRI's Digital Research Infrastructure](#). This document provides the challenges identified by these communities, providing a rich and clear picture of what the UK's leading researchers deem the key challenges for the coming decade.

This report will outline the findings of our investigations. In the following pages you will be able to read about the Grand Challenges identified by the CoSeC communities, the reasons why they are seen as challenges, as well as the processes the communities intend to follow to address them. These range from high-level challenges that stem from key national goals identified in the [2025 Modern Industrial Strategy](#) through to domain-specific drivers that form the long-term plans encapsulated by each community.

The start of this report provides a combined summary across the nine thematic areas of the communities and I believe offers a truly insightful view into how we need to shape research and innovation opportunities over the coming years. This report is a culmination of an enormous amount of combined effort both from within CoSeC's teams and the communities we support and I thank everybody involved.

Dr Stephen Longshaw
CoSeC Director

Executive Summary

This report presents a set of community-defined Grand Challenges spanning engineering, life sciences, mathematics, materials, imaging, astrophysics, quantum computing, digital humanities, and particle physics. While domain-specific, these challenges share common drivers: scale and complexity of data, transition to heterogeneous and exascale computing, integration of AI with physics-based models, the need for validation and trust, and the requirement to make advanced computational capability accessible beyond specialist groups.

Across the communities, a consistent theme emerges within each of the challenges that relate directly to the goals of UKRI's Digital Research Infrastructure:

- Scaling to exascale and utilising heterogeneous compute architectures.
- Integrating AI and ML into modelling workflows.
- Ensuring Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable (FAIR) high-quality data.
- Developing interoperable software ecosystems both across and between communities.
- Training diverse communities of researchers, Research Technical Professionals (RTPs) and domain users.

Together, the CCP and HEC communities outline a roadmap for UK computational research that underpins national priorities in key areas such as **Net Zero, energy security, health, advanced manufacturing, and sovereign capability around digital research infrastructure**. There is convergence on a common goal of creating scalable, energy-efficient, AI-integrated computation that is validated, trusted, and accessible, enabling UK research and industry to exploit digital research infrastructure as a strategic national asset.

Each community-specific area in this report provides an exploration of the domain-specific and application-based drivers that underlie each Grand Challenge. When grouped into thematic areas, it is possible to gain high-level insight into the common threads that exist amongst them.

Engineering

Delivering predictive, validated, and computationally scalable multiphysics simulation for use by industry and on national digital infrastructure.

Across engineering communities (particulate solids, turbulence and wind energy, porous media, wave–structure interaction, and nuclear thermal hydraulics), a key challenge is moving from bespoke or workstation-scale modelling to high-fidelity, validated simulation at real-world scale, capable of informing industrial deployment and regulatory decisions. This requires exploiting heterogeneous HPC (GPUs, large-scale systems, and emerging architectures), integrating AI with solvers, and ensuring access to and curation of high-quality data.

Shared challenges include:

- **Physical scale and performance:** resolving phenomena across metres to hundreds of kilometres (e.g. wind-farm wakes) or nano- to macro-scales (e.g. porous media) demands exascale-class compute capability.
- **Validation and trust:** a lack of open, or available, data limits verification, benchmarking, and regulatory confidence.
- **Industrial usability:** computational cost and complexity inhibit integration into design and operational workflows.

- **Energy efficiency:** rising computing demand must align with Net Zero objectives both in terms of physical and software infrastructure.

Biology

Transforming data-intensive structural and molecular biology into integrated, scalable, and trustworthy computational workflows.

Biology communities (cryo-EM, crystallography, volume electron microscopy, and biomolecular simulation) face explosive growth in data volume and methodological complexity. The challenge is to convert this into reliable, interpretable biological insight at scale, while managing storage, compute cost, and skills.

Shared challenges include:

- **Extreme data scale:** cryo-EM and volume-EM currently generate petabyte-scale datasets that often exceed current analysis and storage paradigms.
- **Integration of AI:** AI is essential for reconstruction, segmentation, and force-field development, but raises issues of validation, bias, and interpretability.
- **Multiscale integration:** coupling quantum, atomistic, coarse-grained, and cellular-scale models into coherent workflows remains an ongoing challenge.
- **Skills and accessibility:** tools must be usable by experimental scientists without deep computational expertise.

Mathematics and Fundamentals

Democratising high-fidelity digital twins beyond elite HPC centres.

The mathematics community (data-driven computational mechanics) identifies that enabling widespread adoption of digital twins across research, engineering, and medicine is key. While digital twins underpin strategic national priority areas, their use remains limited by computational cost and specialist expertise and, importantly, the underlying cross-disciplinary software infrastructure they demand.

Challenges include:

- Making high-fidelity computational models scalable, modular, optimisable and interconnected.
- Integrating real-time data with simulation on often closed computing infrastructure.
- Ensuring that digital twinning research infrastructure is accessible to organisations across a spectrum of computing capability from modest to world-class.

Materials

Preparing materials modelling for AI-enabled, quantum-aware, and energy-efficient next-generation computing.

Materials communities (electronic structure, condensed phases, materials chemistry, and Car–Parrinello methods) face a convergence of scientific ambition and computational constraint. The combined challenge is to extend predictive materials modelling across scales and technologies, whilst exploiting AI and quantum computing and managing energy efficiency.

Shared challenges include:

- **Interoperability with AI and quantum computing:** addressing problems beyond classical computing tractability.
- **Throughput and analysis bottlenecks:** modern simulations often generate data faster than it can be analysed within communities.
- **Reproducibility:** Considered across heterogeneous workflows.
- **Sustaining international collaboration:** Through access to appropriately scaled national computing resources.

Imaging

Evolving imaging from inspection to quantitative, real-time decision making platforms for use in national priority areas such as healthcare.

Imaging communities (tomographic imaging and synergistic biomedical imaging) identify a combined challenge in transforming CT, MRI, and PET from post-inspection tools into real-time quantitative, high-throughput, multimodal platforms for industry and healthcare.

Shared challenges include:

- Handling massive 4D datasets in real time.
- Integrating multimodal and physics-limited data into coherent reconstructions.
- Reducing reliance on proprietary software to enable innovation and reproducibility.
- Ensuring AI-enhanced reconstruction improves diagnostic confidence.

Astrophysics

Sustaining UK leadership in gravitational-wave science through precision, efficiency, and sovereignty.

Numerical relativity faces the dual challenge of increasing mathematical precision to match next-generation gravitational-wave detectors while reducing computational cost and energy use. At the same time, increased reliance on non-UK software infrastructure raises concerns about digital sovereignty with opportunity for organised UK-based communities to make ongoing coherent decisions in the national interest.

Key challenges include:

- Achieving higher precision with fewer computational resources.
- Integrating AI methods without sacrificing reliability or explainability.
- Developing sovereign software capability aligned with future UKRI computing hardware ecosystems.

Quantum Computing

Embedding quantum computing into trusted, regulated research and industrial workflows.

The quantum computing community's challenge is not hardware alone, but early, meaningful integration of quantum computation into existing HPC workflows in a way that delivers real-world research value.

Key challenges include:

- Demonstrating near-term advantage in the areas of chemistry, materials science, and engineering, working with the relevant communities for each.
- Scaling from Noisy Intermediate-Scale Quantum (NISQ)-era devices to modern error-corrected systems.
- Establishing standards, accreditation, and regulatory confidence for quantum-assisted results.

Digital Humanities

Enabling equitable, large-scale AI analysis of cultural heritage and humanities data.

The digital humanities community needs to make trusted AI-enabled analysis of vast cultural datasets accessible to researchers regardless of technical background or institutional resources.

Key challenges include:

- Preparing, curating and delivering heterogeneous digitised and fully-digital collections for analysis.
- Developing and providing shared, scalable and trusted AI inference services.
- Addressing skills gaps and uneven access to digital research infrastructure.

Particle Physics

Transforming computation to meet an order-of-magnitude increase in data and precision.

Particle physics confronts unprecedented data volumes from next-generation experiments both from within the UK and internationally as well as rising demands for theoretical precision. The Grand Challenge is to re-engineer trusted computational methods and software frameworks to enable real-time data processing, simulation, and analysis at large computational scales.

This requires:

- Modular, GPU-accelerated, AI-enhanced workflows.
- Tight integration of theory and experiment and the communities involved.
- Training a researcher workforce within the particle physics communities sufficiently fluent in computational science.

CoSeC Grand Challenges

Over the following pages of this report, we share the Grand Challenges identified by each of the domain-specific CoSeC communities. Each individual community is presented as a case study including a description of the challenge itself, the solution they will implement to address the challenge, and the desired outcome.

CoSeC Sectors

Engineering

The Collaborative Computational Community in Particulate Solids Simulations (CCC-ParaSolS)

CCC-ParaSolS aims to develop cutting-edge software and deliver specialised training to enable the realistic modelling of particulate materials, which are essential to UK industries including chemical, pharmaceutical and construction. Our goal is to provide the particulate community with accurate and efficient frameworks for their modelling needs.

The Community

ParaSolS
Particulate Solids Simulations

www.ccc-parasols.ed.ac.uk

CCC-ParaSolS aims to unite scientists and engineers from academia and industry with a common interest in modelling particulate solids for a variety of applications. Building on existing discipline-specific networks, the community will embed diversity and inclusiveness in its composition, governance, and activities. The community will also promote the use of open-source software and best practices in validation, benchmarking, and research data management. Bespoke training on discrete element methods (DEM), high performance computing (HPC), reproducible research, and FAIR data principles will be delivered by code developers, EPCC, and CoSeC. A training programme will be designed to be inclusive of historically underrepresented groups. Through community consultation, CCC-ParaSolS will identify gaps and barriers in the current modelling capabilities that are inhibiting high-impact scientific discoveries and slowing the transition from workstations to HPC, and from CPUs to GPUs, to improve energy efficiency and performance.

The Challenge

To develop and enable the use of simulation codes at industrially relevant scales for the particulate solids simulation community

Particulate solids are a large and diverse category of materials that include natural soil deposits, mineral ores, pharmaceutical powders and food ingredients. These have significant economic and societal importance. Numerical modelling provides a means to improve efficiency and safety in the vast number of applications that involve particulate solids, by providing insights into the behaviour of these complex granular systems. To enable the modelling of particulate solids at very large scales desired by industry, code developments are essential to effectively exploit modern hybrid computing architectures and derive performance gains from the integration of mechanistic solvers with physics-informed AI. The physical models underpinning simulation codes require additional development to capture the complexity of real-world particulate processes quantitatively and reliably for all applications. Simulation codes need rigorous verification, validation, and benchmarking for which high-quality data from physical experiments are

essential. These data are sometimes lacking and are often not in the public domain. The particulate solids simulation community has historically favoured commercial codes run on workstations, limiting the scale of the problem that can be simulated and not taking advantage of the UK's Digital Research Infrastructure (DRI).

The Solution

To promote and accelerate the development of open-source software for particulate solids simulations

CCC-ParaSolS will promote and accelerate the development of open-source software for particulate solids simulations, which is future-proofed by being deployable on all current and emerging computing architectures found within the UK's DRI, and capable of efficiently utilising computational resources at exascale and beyond. Targeted developments will improve the physical models underpinning simulation codes and integrate multiscale and multiphase modelling capabilities, bringing the community ever closer to capturing the detail and complexity of real particulate solids systems in a virtual environment.

The software suite, including codes for DEM simulations, multi-scale and multi-physics coupling frameworks, visualisation and data analysis, will be comprehensively validated with openly shared data, built on FAIR principles, with AI integrated where advantageous. These technical contributions will ensure that the UK continues to lead in the development and exploitation of particle-scale methods.

The Outcome

A suite of codes for particulate solids simulations available for use for economic and societal benefit in the UK

A suite of high-performance, validated and scalable open-source codes for the numerical modelling of particulate solids will be developed, that democratises the adoption of these codes for economic and societal benefit in the UK. These benefits include reducing waste and increasing process efficiency within numerous sectors of industry, and pre-empting natural disasters caused by climate change. This main goal and the roadmap for CCC-ParaSolS supports UK goals to achieve net zero by 2050 and adapt to the risks posed by climate change without sacrificing economic prosperity. CCC-ParaSolS will be a diverse and inclusive community in accordance with both UKRI's EDI principles and broader goals to create a more equitable society.

More Information

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The Collaborative Computational Project in Turbulence and the UK Turbulence Consortium (CCP Turbulence and UKTC)

To fulfil the ambition of triple wind energy production in 25 years, CCP Turbulence aims to enhance the UK capabilities to simulate complex turbulence problems, whilst UKTC will bring together complementary expertise and strategies to understand, predict and control turbulent flows in High Performance Computing

The Community

www.ukturbulence.co.uk

CCP Turbulence aims to considerably enhance the UK capabilities to simulate complex turbulence problems that were until very recently beyond imagination. Software developments and collaborative activities will not only give UK researchers a unique opportunity to be the first to explore new physics but also be able to answer questions regarding the physics and modelling of turbulent flows found across a range of engineering, physiological and geophysical applications. The UK Turbulence Consortium (UKTC) brings together complementary expertise and co-ordinates activities to look at coherent, rational and strategic ways of understanding, predicting and controlling turbulent flows using High Performance Computing.

The Challenge

To maximize energy output and reduce costs and inefficiencies by actively addressing the issue of the phenomenon known as 'wind theft'

Over the past decade, the UK has solidified its position as a global leader in wind energy, with total installed capacity increasing from 13.6 GW in 2015 to around 30.4 GW in 2024, based on both onshore and offshore wind production. This expansion aligns with the UK Government's Industrial Strategy, which designates Clean Energy Industries as one of eight key sectors driving innovation and economic growth. The strategy emphasizes the beneficial role of wind energy in achieving net zero targets, supporting regional development, and creating high-value jobs. According to the International Energy Agency, the UK aims to deploy up to 50 GW of offshore wind by 2030, with projections suggesting that total wind capacity could reach 100 GW by 2050, potentially supplying over half of the UK's electricity demand alone.

To fulfil the ambition of triple wind energy production in 25 years, major challenges need to be addressed to maximize energy output and reduce costs and inefficiencies. An ever-present problem with wind farm development is the issue of wake interactions among turbines, significantly impacting the farm's total power

output. Recently, due to the increasingly larger size of farms, the issue has expanded at the inter-farm wake interactions level, creating a phenomenon known as "wind theft". Wind theft occurs when upstream wind farms reduce wind speed and energy availability for downstream farms by creating large wakes extending up to 100 km downstream. This has been observed from satellite images of large wind farms across Europe and Asia. Wind theft can lead to reduced energy yield for downstream farms causing economic losses and potential legal disputes between operators. Moreover, inefficiencies in regional energy planning also need to be addressed. Recent studies have highlighted how this issue is becoming more prominent in the North Sea, where dense offshore wind development is underway.

The Solution

To design mitigation strategies and digital twins of real wind farms with high fidelity CFD modelling and simulation methods

To address the challenge of wake interaction at turbine-to-turbine, wind farm, and inter-farm levels, high-fidelity simulations across all these scales—from metres to hundreds or even thousands of kilometres—are essential to design mitigation strategies. These simulations must also incorporate realistic atmospheric flow conditions, complex terrain, and accurately resolved turbine geometries. The vision is to create digital twins of real wind farms so that they can be studied in various configurations. Digital twinning is the creation of a real-time virtual replica of a physical system, that uses data from sensors and other sources to mirror and simulate the behaviour of its real-world counterpart for monitoring, analysis, and optimization purposes.

Modelling and simulation, particularly through high-fidelity Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD), have been instrumental in supporting wind engineering. Within this context, the UK Turbulence Consortium (UKTC) and the CCP Turbulence have played and continue to play a pivotal role in advancing wind engineering research in the UK, particularly with high-performance computing (HPC), high-fidelity Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD), and increasingly, AI-based methods. To optimise the power output of wind farms, there is a clear need for reliable physics-based simulation methods that can faithfully replicate realistic scenarios.

Importantly, to address the challenge of inter-farm wake interactions high fidelity CFD modelling will be a fundamental tool. High-fidelity simulations of an entire wind farm under realistic atmospheric flow conditions and in complex terrain where turbine geometry is well resolved will be mandatory and these will need to interact with regional air flow modelling capable of correctly resolving wake interactions between farms. This will only be possible with exascale and beyond HPC systems and the integration of physical modelling with AI tools for optimization, digital twinning and advanced forecast modelling.

The Outcome

A suite of advanced modelling tools essential to the future security of the UK's wind energy production

As wind energy scales up, these advanced modelling tools will be essential for ensuring fair resource sharing, maximizing output, and supporting evidence-based regulatory frameworks for the future of the UK's wind energy production. These developments will help to inform coordinated planning between neighbouring wind farms.

More Information

CoSeC

www.CoSeC.ac.uk

CoSeC@stfc.ac.uk

CCP Turbulence / UKTC

www.ukturbulence.co.uk

UK Consortium on Mesoscale Engineering Sciences (UKCOMES)

Over the next 5-10 years UKCOMES will continue investigations into the challenging environments of porous media using the Lattice Boltzmann method and taking advantage of emerging computing hardware such as GPUs, Quantum computers and AI.

The Community

www.ucl.ac.uk/mesoscale-modelling-consortium/

The United Kingdom Consortium on Mesoscale Engineering Sciences (UKCOMES) is a group of researchers across the UK who develop and apply mesoscopic modelling techniques to explore systems of scientific and industrial interest at scales between atomistic and continuum levels. The consortium applies and studies several modelling techniques, predominately Dissipative Particle Dynamics (DPD) – a particle-based method similar to atomistic molecular dynamics (MD) – and the Lattice Boltzmann Equation (LBE) method, capable of modelling fluid flows with complex geometries and interactions between multiple fluids and phases. Its core support focuses on developing the consortium’s community codes for DPD and LBE simulations, DL_MESO and HemeLB: adding new functionalities, optimising for various computing architectures (including the UK’s national supercomputer ARCHER2) and improving interoperability with other codes and libraries.

The Challenge

To characterise and model porous media using numerical simulation

Porous media are central to many natural and engineered systems, playing a critical role in renewable energy and sustainable technology developments. Technologies such as fuel cells, batteries, electrolyzers, oil recovery, energy storage and even biological systems (blood vessels, tissues) rely on transport through complex pore networks. Highly coupled multiphysics processes – fluid flow, mass and heat transfer, phase change, and chemical reactions – occur within interconnected pores and strongly influence efficiency, capacity, safety and degradation. Understanding and predicting porous systems often requires quantitative information at the pore scale, where these fundamental mechanisms originate.

Despite their importance, porous media remain challenging to characterise and model due to heterogeneity, hierarchical structure, and dynamic phase interactions. Experimental imaging methods – e.g. X-ray microtomography, focused-ion-beam scanning electron microscopy (FIB-SEM), transmission electron microscopy (TEM) – enable direct visualisation of microstructure and transient processes, but are limited by

spatial resolution, imaging speed, and extreme operating conditions. Analytical approaches work only for idealized geometries, typically neglecting real-world non-linearities. Numerical simulation has thus become essential for investigating pore-scale physics, uncovering underlying mechanisms, and guiding the design of advanced porous materials for energy, environmental and health applications.

The Solution

Using the Lattice Boltzmann method to simulate multiphysics flow in complex porous media

The Lattice Boltzmann Equation (LBE) method has become a versatile and powerful framework for simulating multiphysics flows in complex porous media. Originating from kinetic theory, LBE recovers macroscopic conservation laws – those solved directly by computational fluid dynamics (CFD) methods – while retaining mesoscopic information on particle collisions and momentum exchange. This allows it to capture microstructural effects, interface dynamics and non-equilibrium transport, and to couple hydrodynamics and with thermal, mass transport and chemical fields (reactions). Its local, explicit and highly parallelisable algorithm is well suited to high-performance computing (HPC) platforms, including GPUs and exascale architectures, and naturally handles complex geometries – enabling direct simulation of porous structures derived from micro-CT or FIB-SEM images without generating meshes or transforming coordinates.

Since real porous systems span nano- to macroscale regimes, LBE has been integrated with complementary multiscale techniques, including molecular dynamics (LBE-MD) for nanoconfined gases, pore network methods (LBE-PNM) for multiphase flow and evaporation, discrete element methods (LBE-DEM) for flows in deformable porous media, and finite-volume methods (LBE-FVM) for heat-transfer problems. Recent integration of machine learning (ML) and data-driven models has opened new possibilities, e.g. using large datasets generated from high-fidelity pore-scale LBE simulations to train neural networks and surrogate models to predict permeability, effective diffusivity and interfacial transport. These hybrid LBE-ML approaches greatly reduce computational cost while maintaining physical accuracy, enabling predictive digital twins for porous materials and renewable energy devices.

The Outcome

Using Lattice Boltzmann on emerging computing hardware such as GPUs and Quantum computers and integrating with AI workflows

The UK aims to lead globally in net-zero and health technologies. Understanding, predicting and optimising porous media in these fields is crucial to these ambitions. LBE is highly-suited to porous media simulation, exploiting emerging computing hardware (GPUs, quantum architectures) and integrating seamlessly with AI-driven workflows for accelerated modelling and optimization. As porous media span nano- to macro-scales, increased computational power will enable higher resolution and more reliable predictions.

Key application areas include:

- Next-generation batteries (metal-air, solid-state)
- Hydrogen production and storage (metal-organic frameworks, geological reservoirs)
- Real-time simulation of fluid circulation in human bodies

These systems are notoriously difficult to model using traditional MD or CFD. LBE's flexibility and HPC efficiency enable it to tackle these challenges and make advances ranging from hydrogen-storage design to clinical diagnostics. Future LBE software tools will feature advanced multiphysics solvers (fluid dynamics, heat transfer, phase-change phenomena), and multiscale models linking pore-scale physics to system-level behaviour.

ML techniques will further reduce computational costs, enabling faster insights without sacrificing physical fidelity. This capability is essential for designing and licensing next-generation fission systems, including high temperature gas-cooled reactors and molten salt reactors, priorities within the UK's advanced modular reactor programme and energy security agenda. An AI-enhanced thermal hydraulics framework, validated against international (OECD/NEA) benchmarks, will significantly cut simulation costs, speed up design cycles, provide near real-time operational insights and support digital-twin deployment across reactor types, including Small Modular Reactors and emerging fusion demonstrators.

Building on the UK's strong expertise in high-temperature, high-pressure gas-cooled reactor technologies, a UK-led international validation consortium pool experimental data and develop robust AI/ML frameworks specifically for high-temperature and high-pressure gas-cooled reactor systems.

This roadmap strengthens the UK's ambitions for clean, resilient, sovereign nuclear energy – reinforcing international regulatory leadership, attracting industrial investment, and developing a workforce skilled in multiphysics and AI integration.

More Information

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UKCOMES

www.ucl.ac.uk/mesoscale-modelling-consortium/

The Collaborative Computational Project in Wave Structure Interaction (CCP-WSI / HEC-WSI)

Over the next decade, CCP-WSI will establish itself as the leading UK and international hub for advanced simulation tools in wave-structure interaction towards Net Zero by 2030

The Community

www.ccp-wsi.ac.uk

www.hec-wsi.ac.uk

The Collaborative Computational Project in Wave-Structure Interaction (WSI), brings together two computational communities – fluid dynamics and structural mechanics. This will enable the community to co-design the next generation of Fully Coupled Wave-Structure Interaction (FCWSI) tools with realism both in the flow physics and the structural response, and in this way, unlock new complex applications in ocean and coastal engineering. WSI is primarily focussed on engineering (both computational and experimental) but crosses into other areas such as chemistry, physics and natural (Earth) sciences. Key topics revolve around scientific code coupling, high-performance computing, fluid dynamics, solid mechanics and solid body kinematics, with a focus on community dissemination of methods, software and results with repeatability in mind. Application areas of particular interest include understanding of offshore renewable energy devices (offer wind, wave energy and tidal stream), flood defences and fundamental understanding of the physics of WSI. Increasingly there is also interest in the application of data science topics like AI in the context of surrogate modelling. Their support is split into three key work-packages: WP1: Code Coupling; WP2: Code Performance; WP3: Impact and Sustainability. The work undertaken by CoSeC is intended to be generally applicable to scientific areas of importance to CCP-WSI, as such focus on floating offshore wind turbine design is key, alongside other wave-structure problems, such as violent sloshing of a fluid in a tank.

The Challenge

Lack of data necessary for validating computational models, integrating fluid-structure interaction simulations and supporting multiple software platforms

The UK is a world leader in offshore renewable energy and has committed to delivering up to 60 GW of offshore wind by 2030 as part of its Clean Power, Net Zero and energy security strategies. Achieving these ambitions requires a step change in their ability to model and predict wave–structure interaction (WSI) processes that govern the performance, safety, and sustainability of floating offshore wind turbines, coastal defences, and maritime infrastructure.

Despite progress made by the CCP-WSI community in supporting this goal, their ability to numerical modelling of WSI process faces three critical barriers:

Data Availability for Validation: One of the key challenges is the lack of experimental and field data necessary for validating and calibrating computational models, such as granular/structure models and floating offshore wind turbine coupled models. While CCP-WSI continues to develop advanced models, their capabilities can only be validated through rigorous validation against real-world datasets. Collaborating with industry is essential to access high-quality

field data from real projects, such as floating offshore wind farms. Engaging with experiment labs and leveraging cyber-physical model development will help bridge this gap.

Computational Advancements and Industry Integration: With the rapid evolution of HPC, we are continually optimising our codes to take advantage of parallelisation and partitioned coupling frameworks. However, the computational demands of fully coupled fluid-structure interaction simulations remain high, making them difficult to integrate into industry design workflows. There is a need to develop AI-based surrogate models and reduced-order methods that allow industries to conduct early-stage design assessments before resorting to high-fidelity simulations.

Community Engagement and Cross-Disciplinary Collaboration: CCP-WSI differs from other CCPs in that we support multiple software platforms rather than a single solver. While OpenFOAM is widely used within our community, we recognise the need to collaborate more extensively with other CFD groups and communities, such as the UK Fluids Network and SPH specialists. Expanding collaborations with the AI and computing communities can also provide new opportunities for innovation in model optimisation and data-driven methods.

The Solution

Rigorous validation against real-world datasets, develop AI-based surrogate models and expanding collaborations with the AI and computing communities

Over the next decade, CCP-WSI will establish itself as the leading UK and international hub for advanced simulation tools in wave–structure interaction, underpinned by innovation in numerical modelling, AI, and emerging computer architectures. To achieve this, the community will work closely with industry and experimental facilities to generate high-quality validation datasets from both offshore projects and laboratory studies, supported by cyber-physical approaches and AI-based methods that supplement traditional methods. These efforts will ensure scalable, efficient, and robust validation pipelines, while optimised HPC workflows and AI-based models will accelerate industrial design and reduce computational cost. A central focus will be the development of Grand Challenges and benchmark cases that address both fundamental scientific questions and real-world engineering priorities in offshore renewables, coastal infrastructure, and maritime structures. By aligning these challenges with industry needs, CCP-WSI community will drive targeted research, attract new collaborations, and deliver measurable impact. CAT-WSI will be further developed as a platform for open datasets, benchmarks, codes, and training resources, ensuring transparent and FAIR digital research practices. This platform will also be leveraged to train researchers and RSEs in high-fidelity modelling, AI/ML, and HPC workflows in collaboration with CoSeC and the wider CCP network. To broaden impact, CCP-WSI will strengthen cross-disciplinary and international partnerships, extending collaborations with the AI, quantum computing and data-centric computational mechanics communities. Internationally, they will build on the strong profile of CCP-WSI blind tests to establish joint facilities, common standards, and shared datasets, including through European partnerships and global consortia. Finally, the community will foster a vibrant and diverse skills base, supporting RSE career development through pooled training, networking, and exchange opportunities. This integrated roadmap will ensure CCP-WSI community continues to advance world-class digital infrastructure, strengthen sovereign capability in offshore engineering, and accelerate the deployment of clean, resilient, and sustainable marine and offshore energy technologies.

The Outcome

Accelerating floating offshore wind deployment to achieve Net Zero by 2030

Addressing these challenges directly supports national strategic priorities. The work aligns with UK Government goals by accelerating floating offshore wind deployment to achieve Clean Power 2030 and Net Zero 2050 targets, strengthening the capability in offshore engineering for the Energy Security Strategy, and enabling sustainable coastal infrastructure in line with Maritime 2050. It also advances UKRI DRI priorities by delivering interconnected DRI through federated workflows linking OpenFOAM, SPH, and AI-based surrogate models; training RSEs and researchers in high-fidelity modelling, AI/ML, and HPC workflows; promoting FAIR via open datasets and benchmarks released through CAT-WSI as a digital asset; and fostering sustainability by implementing efficient algorithms and surrogate modelling to reduce HPC costs, energy use, and carbon footprint.

More Information

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CCP-WSI

www.ccp-wsi.ac.uk

The Collaborative Computational Project in Nuclear Thermal Hydraulics CCP-NTH

The vision of the CCP-NTH community is to develop advanced modelling tools which incorporate the latest development in digital technologies and numerical algorithms, to improve nuclear reactor design and safety to help meet the UK's energy security goals and Net Zero commitments.

The Community

www.ccpnth.ac.uk

Next-generation nuclear reactors, that are currently under development, are aimed at achieving inherent safety using technologies, such as passive cooling. Such systems require a significantly advanced thermal-hydraulics approach to deal with much higher temperature pressure systems and/or non-conventional coolants, such as liquid metal and molten salts. The traditional methodology is insufficient to deal with the new challenges to be encountered. The aim of CCP-NTH is to support a community of researchers and engineers to develop and maintain computational methods and software packages which will modernise nuclear thermal hydraulics tools. These tools will meet the demands imposed through the development of advanced next generation nuclear reactor systems to be employed in the coming decades.

The Challenge

To transform computational thermal hydraulics capabilities that support the design, operation, and safety of nuclear reactors.

To meet the UK's energy security goals and Net Zero commitments, there is an urgent need to transform computational thermal hydraulics capabilities that support the design, operation, and safety of nuclear reactors. As the UK moves toward a low carbon and secure energy future, nuclear power continues to play a central role, and it is becoming increasingly important to develop advanced modelling tools that combine multiple physics processes operate across different scales and incorporate the latest digital technologies. These tools are essential for improving reactor design, ensuring safety, and supporting regulatory decisions. A key challenge is to accurately represent complex physical phenomena such as boiling, turbulence, and heat transfer under extreme conditions inside reactors.

The Solution

To develop advanced modelling tools incorporating AI and machine learning techniques that are accurate and scalable.

The UK TH community are inspired to develop next-generation thermal-hydraulics tools that are not only accurate and scalable, but also making use of AI-driven workflows. These tools will include advanced Multiphysics solvers that couple fluid dynamics, heat transfer, and phase-change phenomena, as well as multiscale models that bridge fine-scale physics with system-level behaviour.

Machine learning techniques will be applied to reduce computational costs and enable faster, real-time insights without compromising physical accuracy. An AI-enhanced computational thermal hydraulics modelling framework, validated against multinational datasets, once developed will dramatically reduce simulation costs, accelerate design cycles, provide near real-time operational insights, and shorten licensing timelines.

The Outcome

Safe and efficient design of next-generation fission systems with CCP-NTH as a national hub for AI-enhanced thermal hydraulics platforms.

These capabilities are essential for the safe and efficient design and licensing of next-generation fission systems, including high temperature gas-cooled reactors and molten salt reactors, both of which are strategic priorities under both the UK's advanced modular reactor programme and energy security agenda. Overcoming technicalities is crucial for building trust in simulations, reducing uncertainty, and speeding up the development of next generation nuclear technologies.

These improvements will strengthen public and regulatory confidence and support the UK's leadership in clean, secure, and innovative nuclear energy. CCP-NTH will support this leadership, reinforcing its position in international regulatory benchmarks, attracting industrial investment, and cultivating a skilled workforce in multiphysics and AI integration. CCP-NTH aims to serve as a national hub for validated, AI-enhanced thermal hydraulics platforms, driving safe, low-carbon innovation across both fission and fusion reactor technologies.

More Information

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Biology

The Collaborative Computational Project for Electron cryo-Microscopy (CCP-EM)

In the next 5-10 years, CCP-EM will enable software development and large-scale computing support to create state-of-the-art CryoEM/T methods to develop life-changing drug discoveries

The Community

The Collaborative Computational Project for Electron cryo-Microscopy (cryoEM) provides support in computational areas for users and developers in biological cryoEM. CCP-EM serves the worldwide cryoEM community by providing software and training to users, researchers and developers of cryoEM software; it also provides a focal point for the cryoEM community to interact with related communities via CoSeC. It's UKRI/STFC licensed software suite enables end users to efficiently process their data and solve structures whilst supporting the software developer community to develop and distribute novel tools using both classical and ML/AI algorithms.

The Challenge

To develop new computational tools and techniques to aid drug discovery, improve storage efficiency and speed of data processing

Cryogenic-sample Electron Microscopy (cryoEM) is one of the principal methods for solving structures of proteins, and other biomolecules, to near atomic resolution. The field has seen an exponential increase in use over the previous decade due to improvements in microscope hardware and image processing software, crowned by the award of the Nobel Prize for Chemistry in 2017. CryoEM is now a primary driver in structural biology and >£50M has been invested by many, including Wellcome, MRC, BBSRC to ensure access to essential high-end equipment for the UK life science sector. During the COVID-19 pandemic, cryoEM played an essential role in understanding the molecular basis of the disease, aiding the development of effective vaccines and other therapeutics. This method is now routinely used in novel drug discovery and allows biomolecules not amenable to other biophysical techniques to be studied, which is of particular importance for neurodegenerative diseases such as Alzheimer's and Parkinsons. CCP-EM serves the worldwide cryoEM community by providing software and training. As the field has expanded CCP-EM has taught over 1600 researchers from across the world in the last 10 years and the annual 'CCP-EM Spring Symposium' conference is now the principal cryoEM meeting in the UK with over 1000 delegates in 2025. Much of work described above has focused on studying macromolecules *in vitro* i.e. isolated from their cellular environment but in recent years breakthroughs in electron tomography (cryoET) have allowed researchers to observe protein at high resolution in their native environment. This promises to bring a new dawn in drug discovery and, more broadly, fundamentally enhance our understanding of life at the molecular level. CCP-

EM is actively developing computational tools in this area though there are many challenges to overcome, such as object identification and heterogenous reconstruction. CryoEM is highly data intensive image processing with large demands for compute power and storage. The field produces ~400Pb of data per year, a vast amount on par with the Square Kilometre Array. The Electron Bio-Imaging Centre (eBIC) at the Diamond Light Source (DLS) currently generates ~10Pb data per year and CCP-EM is helping develop new compression protocols to improve storage efficiency, which will be of benefit to the wider community. CCP-EM is also evolving GPU accelerated image processing routines to improve the speed of data processing and both initiatives will help reduce the carbon cost of data analysis and storage.

The Solution

Develop state-of-the-art computational support for essential biophysical methods

To keep its world leading position, the UK life science sector must have state-of-the-art computational support for essential biophysical methods. CCP-EM are targeting the following areas for development: 1) improved workflows for resolving protein:ligand complexes for drug discovery; 2) develop heterogenous reconstruction algorithms to yield molecular movies allowing researchers capture different states of molecular machines; 3) develop new methods for cryo-tomography using AI/ML where appropriate and 4) data/metadata management to handle the increasing data volumes, and ensure that database entries are well annotated and FAIR. CCP-EM will continue to support key facilities at Harwell Campus as well as its extensive training programme. Long-term external contributions are essential for CCP-EM, with an extensive network including amongst others, the Crick, MRC-LMB, EMBL-EBI, TU Delft and the Universities of Cambridge, Tokyo, and Princeton. CCP-EM works closely with the current related life science CCPs within CoSeC: CCP4, CCPN and CCPBioSim, which was recently strengthened by the DRIIMB (Digital Research Infrastructure for Integrated Molecular Biology) initiative, helping CCPs that support highly specialised fields to work together.

The Outcome

Facilitating innovative cryoEM/T methods enabling new therapeutics in structural biology

Over the next decade CCP-EM will continue drive software development and large-scale computing support to facilitate state of the art cryoEM/T methods for the next generation of structural biologists that will in turn enable new therapeutics by providing essential tools and training for researchers in both the academic and industrial sectors.

More Information

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CCP-EM

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The Collaborative Computational Project Number 4 in Protein Crystallography (CCP4)

Over the next ten years, CCP4 will transform into a unified AI-enhanced, hybrid-structured biology platform that integrates multiple experimental modalities with cutting-edge computational methods

The Community

www.ccp4.ac.uk

CCP4 aims to produce and support a world-leading, integrated suite of programs that allows researchers to determine macromolecular structures by X-ray crystallography, and other biophysical techniques. Integrating cutting-edge approaches, experimental determination and detailed analysis into protein structure is key to the development of this suite. CCP4 is a community-based resource that supports the widest possible researcher community, embracing academic, not-for-profit, and for-profit research. CCP4 endeavours to play a key role in the education and training of scientists in experimental structural biology, and encourages the wide dissemination of new ideas, techniques and practice.

The Challenge

Overcoming the emerging complexities that obstruct the path from experimental data to trusted macromolecular model

Structural biology underpins modern bioscience and drug discovery. CCP4 enables macromolecular structure determination by using X-ray crystallography, which is crucial in the understanding of biological processes and the development of new therapeutics against diseases. However, the path from experimental data to macromolecular models faces growing complexity, due to the emergence of hybrid models that integrate data from a range of sources, including X-ray diffraction, computational models, cryo-EM, NMR, Molecular Dynamics, and biophysical / biochemical analyses. This generates novel type models that encompass the dynamic nature of macromolecules and subsequently, CCP4 is evolving from a crystallography-only platform to a truly integrative structural biology environment.

Key challenges ahead include the incorporation of AI-generated information, integrating various data sources like crystallography and AlphaFold predictions, to ensure seamless workflows. There are difficulties with data quality, as AI needs to enhance non-optimal datasets and manage imperfect data efficiently. Scalability and automation are crucial as modern facilities generate vast datasets requiring real-time processing. Trust, reproducibility, and validation are essential for regulatory compliance, demanding clear systems. Lastly, training and accessibility must improve to support both beginners and experts in the global structural biology

community while addressing the complexities of large datasets. The large complex datasets generated from AI and complex methods, however, provide a challenge for training.

Community and workforce development will be crucial:

- Expanded training resources, including interactive tutorials, and cloud-based practice platforms.
- Cultivating the next generation of structural biologists with strong foundations in computation, statistics, and AI.
- Enable the community to understand and evaluate AI generated information, such as computational structures, hybrid models, and predictions.

The Solution

Transform into a unified AI-enhanced, hybrid platform that integrates experimental modalities with cutting-edge methods

In the next ten years, CCP4 will further the interoperability and cooperation with the wider research community by transforming into a unified AI-enhanced, hybrid-structural-biology platform that integrates multiple experimental modalities with cutting-edge computational methods. CCP4 will fully integrate the use of AI for modelling and validation, incorporating machine learning and intelligent model building. Seamless hybrid pipelines will combine frameworks, inform experiment design and accelerate structure solution. The creation of digital twins for biomolecular systems will real-time feedback from experiments to optimize data collection, together with a focus on managing data and metadata for interoperability, utilizing large language models to capture important textual information. Data sharing and benchmarking to validate AI-driven algorithms is essential, and will assist in the expansion of training resources, such as interactive tutorials and cloud-based practice platforms.

The Outcome

Recognised as the global benchmark for crystallographic software by expanding into a hub for integrative structural biology

Accelerating discovery in biomedicine, biotechnology, and fundamental biology, CCP4 will maintain the role as the global benchmark for crystallographic software by expanding into a hub for integrative structural biology. CCP4 will be supporting both academic discovery and industrial drug development; enable faster, more reliable, and reproducible structure solutions and secure the UK's and CCP4's global leadership in structural biology innovation.

More Information

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Building a Collaborative Computational Project for Volume Electron Microscopy (CCP-volumeEM)

Over the next five to ten years, CCP-volumeEM will help the community to realise the full capabilities of this sought after technology by adopting and disseminating the latest computational methods

The Community

Imaging biological material across functional length scales and at high resolution

VolumeEM (vEM) is a group of techniques that are used to image biological material through continuous depths of at least one micrometre at nanometre resolution. vEM is applied extensively in neuroscience to image brain tissue in sufficient detail to map the wiring of neurons. vEM techniques are now being applied to a wide range of biological systems, bridging the gap between the functional imaging of fluorescence microscopy and the molecular detail of cryoEM. The scientific value of insights that have been made possible via vEM have placed this family of techniques amongst the most important scientific technologies of recent years, having been named as one of the “Seven technologies to watch in 2023” by *Nature*, and as the second most requested technology of 2024 in the Euro-Bioimaging Annual Report. vEM techniques use highly automated instruments that are capable of producing data well into the multi-terabyte regime per sample, leading to many challenges in data management, processing and interpretation. AI techniques are becoming widespread to automate the identification of features in complex data, and there is a pressing need for a collaborative community to coordinate and standardise efforts in the field.

The Challenge

Overcoming sheer scale of data, lack of training, limited data formats, financial and experimental costs and ethical imperatives

Historically, much image analysis performed in biological vEM has involved a great deal of manual effort, since many of the computational methods that work well in other imaging modalities, such as fluorescence microscopy, are unable to perform adequately with the complexities of vEM data. Recent years have seen AI based analysis methods begin to perform well in some applications, particularly in the area of “segmentation”, an image analysis process used to delineate objects of interest from their surroundings. However, the typical AI problems of obtaining suitable training data and creating models that are sufficiently generalised to work across the necessary range of data are commonplace and can typically only be overcome by significant community effort. A major challenge to the robust usage of modern computational techniques in vEM is the sheer scale of the data, as well as the broad range of backgrounds of the various

stakeholders, with many end-users being biologists with little-to-no formal training in computational methods. Bridging these experimental-to-computational domain boundaries is a familiar problem in bioimage analysis more generally, especially where much of the accumulated knowledge and tooling has grown organically over many years into a very heterogeneous ecosystem deployed across multiple incompatible platforms. Prevailing image data formats in use are generally bitmap-style formats like TIFF and a range of proprietary formats, which need to be loaded directly into RAM, placing hard limits on the size of data that can be analysed without downscaling or cropping. As datasets get larger and more complex, the resulting lack of standardisation or community-established best practices for dealing with larger-than-RAM data has led to a hard-to-navigate landscape, with much missing functionality. These difficulties often result in limited extraction of information from the incredibly rich, dense datasets typical of vEM. As well as the associated experimental costs, there are also ethical imperatives to ensure that data from clinical or animal studies are used effectively, squeezing maximum scientific benefit from each experiment, in accordance with the [UKRI principle](#) of Replacement, Refinement and Reduction of animals in research.

The Solution

Harnessing AI technologies, integrating image processing functionalities and adopting standards for multimodal data

The advances in imaging instrumentation and computational techniques used in vEM show no sign of slowing down, and the ability to flexibly adopt new and emerging computational methods will be key to ensure the activities of CCP-volumeEM remain at the forefront. In particular, harnessing the rapid evolution of AI techniques will benefit greatly from increased standardisation and modularity in workflow-building principles and implementation, as well as from the sharing of FAIR datasets in public repositories. A comprehensive integration of next generation file formats (NGFF)-enabled image processing functionalities into end-user accessible software tools and interfaces will allow transparent-to-the-user incorporation of the latest technologies but will require significant developer effort to achieve full coverage. Such endeavours have been largely neglected under traditional funding and publication models due to their long-term nature – however, a CCP is an ideal custodian of such critical development activities. Another rapidly advancing frontier in biology research is the use of multimodal data, whether that's multiple imaging modalities, for example volume correlative light and electron microscopy (vCLEM), or experiments also incorporating genetic, molecular and other data types. In this context, the cross-cutting activities of CoSeC will be crucial, enabling CCP-volumeEM to work with other CCPs and HECs, for example CCP-EM, CCP4, HECBioSim and others, in order to ensure effective cross-domain communication and standardisation to unlock the possibilities that such multimodal methods promise.

The Outcome

Bridging experimental to computational domain boundaries with new computational technologies that can enable efficient analysis of large datasets

By fostering a community of stakeholders from across the whole spectrum of domain experts and end-users, CCP-volumeEM will support the development and maintenance of a range of resources that will allow practitioners to access a set of high-quality, interoperable, and benchmarked tools and libraries. Through the promotion of NGFF, which use a chunked storage strategy to enable lazy-loading of data, the ability to efficiently visualise, process and analyse these ever-growing datasets will be enhanced. New functionality to provide standard image processing operations to NGFF data will be available to enable efficient processing and analysis of such datasets. In addition, the establishment of appropriate schemas and ontologies will enable the rich experimental and imaging metadata to be recorded in consistent formats that allow the prospect of much more extensive mining and re-use of these high value datasets.

Key deliverables for this will be the sharing of public resources such as containerised builds of tried-and-tested collections of tools that can be deployed on any platforms, from laptops to HPC and cloud infrastructure. Exemplar workflows demonstrating the use of NGFF will be shared and documented thoroughly to demonstrate how to sustainably build pipelines for other use-cases, using research software engineering and data stewardship best practices. Associated training materials will be created and delivered to provide taught and self-guided resources for the community. The developer community will be grown through a series of focused hackathons, interfacing with related communities where appropriate.

More Information

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CCP-vEM

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(in development)

The Collaborative Computational Project for Biomolecular Simulation (CCPBioSim)

Over the next five to ten years, a key challenge for biomolecular simulation is to couple our different computational tools together into multi-scale models that propagate information from the regime of quantum chemistry up towards the cellular level

The Community

www.ccpbiosim.ac.uk

CCPBioSim promotes the use of computer simulations for understanding biological molecules and their function. Many of these simulations provide information that is inaccessible or difficult to obtain experimentally, such as biomolecular dynamics. Running training, conferences and supporting software development, CCPBioSim cares about building an inclusive and creative community where everyone interested in biomolecular simulations is welcome and encouraged to learn and share knowledge to produce the best science possible, including experimental teams who need simulation to gain further insight from their data. As well as basic science, CCPBioSim develop the next generation of methods for computational drug-discovery, which is becoming increasingly complex as drugs move away from being simple small molecules towards biologics such as antibodies, affimers, nucleic acid therapeutics, proteolysis targeting chimeras (PROTACs) and molecular glues that form bioactive ternary protein complexes. The use of GPUs has massively increased the use of biomolecular simulations by industry, because they have improved the efficiency of methods that were previously too slow. Showcasing the most exciting simulations and tools and interfacing with experiments and industry, CCPBioSim continuously works on sharing expertise within their highly multidisciplinary community.

The Challenge

Expanding the length and time-scales accessible to biomolecular simulations

Dynamics plays a role in biology right down to the atomic level. Dynamics and flexibility are important in the catalytic function of enzymes, and in the free energy changes driving molecular recognition, which is the key process in rational drug design. Molecular machines, which burn chemical energy to perform work, necessarily require dynamics to perform their functions, and perform many vital jobs such as processing DNA and carrying cargos around the cell.

Physics based models such as molecular dynamics (MD) are well established as tools for calculating biomolecular dynamics from structures obtained experimentally (or from AlphaFold). These methods

compute the ensemble of conformations of a biological molecule at room temperature using a molecular mechanics energy function and an empirical forcefield. Fully atomistic simulations of single proteins or small protein complexes in explicit solvent can typically explore microsecond timescales. Coarse-grained simulations using Brownian Dynamics and ridged protein models can represent sections of the eukaryotic cytoplasm, and sections of protein-bound eukaryotic and bacterial membranes. Even larger length-scales right up to whole cell models require continuum mechanics simulations, and/or reaction diffusion models. Our first Grand Challenge is to improve the efficiency and accuracy of our existing methods, for example by using the machine learning/artificial intelligence (ML/AI) methods currently under development to provide better forcefields. A second key Grand Challenge for biomolecular simulation is to couple our different computational tools together into a multi-scale dynamic model that propagates information from the atomistic through to the cellular level, and vice versa.

The Solution

Integrated workflows for modelling biomolecular dynamics at multiple scales

To understand dynamic systems such as molecular machines, metabolic networks or the formation (and disassembly) of cellular architectures such as the cytoskeleton we need multi-scale computational models. We also need to include omics data sets into our models, as these provide information about the chemical composition of cellular structures. This requires the coupling of different software methods together into organised workflows, and will need to be computationally efficient on HPC/HTC platforms to achieve the necessary throughput. We will also need to be able to make our tools usable and understandable across multiple domain boundaries, which requires, for example, complex physics based workflows to be accessible to experimental biologists.

The Outcome

Improved design tools for drug discovery and biotechnology

A better understanding of biomolecular dynamics across multiple scales is essential if we are to fully understand the relationship between biomolecular structure and function. The biggest biological questions, such as how drugs which operate at the molecular level affect the whole organism, or how genome instability leads to cancer will remain unanswered unless we apply a combination of different biophysical tools, including simulations. The benefits will be improved design tools for the pharmaceutical industry, and a better understanding of pathogens and how we might prevent, diagnose and cure disease. There is also the potential for entirely new biotechnologies, such as designed proteins or molecular motors that are novel active materials, that perform bespoke mechanical activities at the nanoscale.

More Information

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The High-End Computing Consortium for Biomolecular Simulation (HECBioSim)

Over the next five to ten years, a key challenge for biomolecular simulation is to bring together Simulation and AI to tackle multi-interfacial problems at larger time and length scales.

The Community

www.hecbiosim.ac.uk

HECBioSim promotes the use of UK High Performance Computing facilities amongst researchers in the biomolecular simulation domain as well as increasing the uptake by non-traditional users and experimentalist scientists interested in the application of molecular simulations to specific problems. Molecular simulations provide high resolution information about the dynamics of biomolecules and complex systems which is often the link between structure and function – such high resolution and details of dynamics are difficult to obtain by experimental methods alone. HECBioSim since its inception has been responsible for allocation of resources on Tier1 (ARCHER2) and subsequently also several UK TIER2 via its Resource Allocation Panels. It develops high performance workflow tooling as well as supporting HPC centres with software installation and optimisation. HECBioSim supports its sister consortium CCPBioSim by providing workshops and training on HPC best practice and run-time optimisation. HECBioSim maintains a benchmark suite that has become the international *de-facto* standard for characterisation of simulation performance for all major codes in the biomolecular simulations domain. We support UK applicants for HPC resources through information on our website, tailored advice and through specialised resource calculators we have developed. HECBioSim is open to new members, and anyone in the remit area with a full-time UK position in academia may submit a proposal to our Resource Allocation Panels for UK HPC time.

The Challenge

Tackling problems at larger scales and integrating next generation technologies into simulation workflows.

The landscape of both technology and science has changed significantly over the last 5 years. On the technology front, we have seen the advent and rise of data intensive computing, much of which falls under the AI umbrella. Within biomolecular science, most notably structure prediction technologies, such as AlphaFold3 and machine learnt interatomic potentials offer a wealth of new opportunities. We have also seen an explosion in the diversity of HPC architectures with new vendors entering the HPC market with innovative solutions in both the CPU and GPU hardware spaces. The scientific landscape has experienced a shift from classic sources of protein structures such as X-Ray diffraction and Nuclear Magnetic Resonance

which were somewhat limited to smaller structures, towards imaging-based methods such as Cryo-Electron Microscopy and Electron Tomography - this has brought a vast wealth of new structural data of larger structures and more complex systems.

Addressing the next generation of pressing biological questions in the biomolecular simulation space, is going to require pushing our codes and methods beyond their current capabilities. Accessing the time and length scales required for compatibility with evolving experimental techniques requires not only a step change in how our codes and methods scale but also radical increases in the community accessible computational resources. Furthermore, physics-based simulation and AI are clearly complementary and for understanding the structure-dynamics-function relationships of biomolecules they are usually co-dependent and thus not substitutes for each other, but rather support and enhance each others capabilities and scope.

The integration of AI and simulation such that they augment each other to enable tackling problems that are currently out of scope for both presents an interesting engineering problem. Currently used HPC platforms and software workflows are not engineered for such multimodal approaches, consequently our significant challenges in the future are ones around technology and doing the necessary engineering that will allow us to address the most pressing science questions of tomorrow.

The Solution

Engineering platforms and workflows to greater enable researchers to deploy next generation science.

To successfully push our current biomolecular simulations capabilities to enable new discoveries by incorporating AI and scaling to extended spatio-temporal scales we must appropriately evolve the engineering of the whole UK HPC ecosystem. The current generation of HPC are not configured to enable fully multimodal workflows, where simulation and AI can run side-by-side and exchange real-time information. We must engineer the software frameworks to enable researchers to build, configure and deploy reproducibly such complex workflows. We must do this at the next generation of HPC scale and across a diverse array of hardware configurations than has existed in the past decade. Further engineering of our codes and the tooling that support running them is required to enable researchers to define problems which require our codes to talk to next generation technologies such as AI across a wider array of interfaces into the simulation pipeline.

The Outcome

Exploiting next generation platforms and technologies will fertilise new research areas with exceptional potential in healthcare.

Biology is inherently complex and multidimensional with problems ranging from those that focus on individual molecules up to entire human body, even at the minute scale problems are still highly multi-scale in nature ranging from small molecules up to the whole human cell.

Understanding more about how these biological systems behave and function at each scale leads to direct application in the design and discovery of new therapeutics and beneficial outcomes for our society.

More Information

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Mathematics

Towards a CCP in Data-driven Computational Mechanics (CCP-DCM)

Over the next decade, digital twins will become central to engineering, healthcare, climate modelling, and manufacturing. Their role will expand from isolated simulations to adaptive, data-driven systems capable of real-time prediction, optimisation, and decision support. However, widespread use demands robust, scalable computational models accessible beyond elite HPC centres. Here, CCP-DCM will be crucial: by advancing open, efficient, and user-friendly numerical methods for solving partial differential equations—the backbone of digital twin physics—it will democratize access to high-fidelity modelling. Through CoSeC's community-driven software, training, and cross-domain collaboration, CCP-DCM will help ensure digital twins evolve from specialised research tools into everyday enablers of innovation across UK academia and industry.

The Community

ccp-dcm.github.io

CCP-DCM is a CCP centred around the FEniCS and Firedrake software frameworks for the numerical solution of partial differential equations (PDEs). These numerical simulations are essential for advancing science and engineering across a very broad range of disciplines. FEniCS and Firedrake are used to develop solvers in the geosciences (ocean, atmosphere, cryosphere, geodynamics), nuclear fusion (plasma, tritium transport, breeding blankets), physiology and medicine (brain, heart), and many more besides.

The Challenge

Widespread adoption of faithful digital twins across computational science and engineering

The grand challenge of the CCP-DCM is to enable the widespread adoption of faithful digital twins across computational science and engineering. A digital twin is a high-fidelity, multiphysics simulation that integrates real-time or historical data from a physical system. Its purpose is to replicate the behaviour of the system with sufficient accuracy to support design decisions, operational insights, and scientific discovery. A well-known example is numerical weather prediction, which combines complex physical models with rapid assimilation of observational data to produce accurate forecasts.

Extending this paradigm to other engineered and natural systems opens the door to value-driven science, where costly and time-consuming physical experiments can be replaced—or augmented—by efficient, predictive simulations.

The Solution

Democratising digital twin technology to be available to all with modest computational resources

The core challenge lies in democratising digital twin technology: making it accessible to engineering firms and research groups with modest computational resources, rather than requiring the infrastructure of national laboratories or weather centres. The CCP-DCM community is uniquely positioned to address this challenge through its expertise in composable and modular modelling frameworks, automated code generation, and differentiable programming—enabling flexible, scalable, and optimisable simulations that integrate seamlessly with data-driven workflows.

The Outcome

Supporting the core simulation toolchain with digital twin technology fully integrated across computational science and engineering

CCP-DCM will be actively supporting and developing the core simulation toolchain to enable current and new users to continue pushing the limits in simulation scale. Digital twin technology will have been fully developed and integrated across organizations and research groups across computational science and engineering.

More Information

CoSeC

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CCP-DCM

ccp-dcm.github.io

Materials

The Collaborative Computational Project Number 9: Computational Electronic Structure of Condensed Matter (CCP9)

First principles materials modelling is the keystone of modern technology, allowing us to understand, exploit and design materials with the special properties we need. CCP9 supports materials modelling by maintaining high-performance simulation codes, conducting pioneering theoretical research and by fostering the UK community of material simulation specialists.

The Community

www.ccp9.ac.uk

CCP9 was established in 1980 to advance methods and code development in the UK materials modelling community. Since then, CCP9 has provided a crucial network connecting UK-based research groups in electronic structure, coordinating both research and software engineering activities and organising training in the theory and application of coding. Their collaboration, coordination and community elements have significantly contributed to gaining and maintaining UK leadership in theoretical materials science.

The Challenge

To meet and fulfil the growing demands of a new, multiscale simulation paradigm spanning diverse technology fields

Technology and engineering priorities place huge challenges on the Electronic Structure community as we continue to develop methods for delivering clearer science insight and answers to ever more complicated questions. The main challenges before us are to integrate and fully utilise new approaches to science: **Interoperability with AI**, which will allow us to not only accelerate our codes but also automate their execution and help with analysis of outputs; **Interoperability with Quantum Computing**, which will allow solution to previously unsolvable physics problems; and, **Black-box like precision and reliability** enabling our methods to be deployed without laborious human control. And as our codes scale to use ever larger computational facilities, we must pay serious attention to **Energy efficiency and new architecture exploitation**.

The Solution

Interoperability with both AI and quantum computing, energy efficiency and new architecture adoption

AI/LLM technologies will be used to accelerate first principles materials modelling by optimising the selection of specific materials cases and properties for calculation, by automating the preparation of calculation inputs, by accelerating or improving algorithms in the electronic structure codes and, even, by providing new, more efficient approximations for the fundamental theories that our codes implement (eg, approximations for the unsolvable electron-electron correlation problem).

As quantum hardware becomes available with sufficient capability for real calculations, we will develop the algorithms that are needed for their use. Condensed matter physics and computational chemistry areas are the first application areas for this new technology and we expect quantum computers will make possible previously unsolvable problems, or else attain huge efficiency gains, compared with current modelling approaches.

Historically, calculations using electronic structure theory were limited by available resources, codes and level of theory; reproducibility and accuracy were less important than the specific scientific insight afforded by calculations to scientists' specific projects. The expert user (who usually authored the code) was indispensable. CCP9 will adopt a new modelling paradigm where electronic structure calculations will be applied as part of (potentially hugely) complex studies working across scales from the atomic to the gigantic. Numerical and other errors will be understood, quantified and become systematically controllable, allowing our methods to be deployed successfully by AI-enabled non-experts working in widely different topics.

The Outcome

A suite of codes that can be applied routinely by non-experts in complex, AI-enabled workflows

The CCP9 community will build upon its global leadership in electronic structure to provide a suite of codes that can be applied routinely by non-experts in complex, AI-enabled workflows in simulation areas extending well beyond the materials science area. Quantum computing will be added to the CCP9 portfolio of state-of-the-art methods enabling new simulation possibilities.

More Information

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CCP9

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The Collaborative Computational Project Number 5 in Computer Simulation of Condensed Phases (CCP5)

Over the next five to ten years, CCP5 will develop a suite of new processing tools for the simulation of condensed phases via sustainable strategies to enable innovative discoveries

The Community

www.ccp5.ac.uk

CCP5 is the UK's Collaborative Computational Project focused on the computer simulation of condensed-phase materials. Established over 40 years ago to strengthen national collaboration, CCP5 provides researchers across universities and public laboratories with free access to an extensive suite of supported and contributed software for non-commercial use. This open-access model fosters strong industrial engagement through workshops, conferences, and dedicated industry-focused events. CCP5's remit spans atomistic to mesoscopic simulations, bringing together diverse expertise to enable world-class research that is both scientifically ambitious and cost-effective. The UK hosts one of the world's most active and successful communities in condensed-phase simulation, and CCP5 plays a central role in coordinating communication, sharing best practices, and supporting emerging research directions. With a strong international profile, CCP5 maintains and develops leading simulation codes, enhances software functionality, and supports the community in delivering innovative science at the forefront of materials modelling.

The Challenge

To advance machine learning, reproducibility, and data infrastructure for next-generation molecular simulation

Molecular modelling now produces data at a scale that exceeds our ability to analyse and exploit it. While machine learning already delivers major advances in force-field development and shows promise across the modelling workflow, current ML models still lack the robustness and transferability needed for real-world materials and chemistry problems. Meanwhile, modern supercomputers generate molecular dynamics trajectories faster than today's predominantly serial analysis tools can process them, creating a widening performance bottleneck. High-throughput screening and complex multi-software workflows are feasible on advanced HPC and cloud platforms, but they generate vast, heterogeneous datasets that must be efficiently analysed, made FAIR, and integrated into reproducible pipelines. Addressing these challenges requires scalable trajectory analysis tools, deeper and more reliable ML integration, interoperable data infrastructures, and automated end-to-end workflows that keep pace with rapidly expanding simulation capabilities.

The Solution

GPU-enabled analysis, strong validation frameworks, and FAIR data ecosystems together provide the foundation for next-generation, simulation-driven materials discovery

These challenges can be addressed by accelerating the most computationally demanding analysis tools through GPU-native implementations, which are now feasible due to the widespread availability of modern accelerator hardware. Rigorous validation and benchmarking are essential to ensure that data-driven force fields and ML models perform reliably in real-world applications. Equally important are new strategies that improve reproducibility, reusability, and long-term data stewardship. A robust Python-based workflow infrastructure plays a central role here: it enables automation, data provenance, and the seamless management and sharing of complex high-throughput simulation pipelines. Although such infrastructures have traditionally supported quantum mechanical workflows, they are now being extended to classical molecular dynamics, allowing researchers to run large simulation campaigns, track the full history of each result, and store outputs in FAIR-compliant formats. By building on existing CCP5 tools, the community can streamline the use of multiple MD codes, unify data handling, and ensure scalable, reproducible, and GPU-accelerated analysis for next-generation molecular simulation.

The Outcome

An end-to-end ecosystem of interoperable, GPU-ready tools with FAIR data foundations that supports rigorous structure-function analysis and the computational development of advanced materials.

A suite of GPU-accelerated post-processing tools will be available by 2027, enabling trajectory analysis and data handling to scale with modern high-performance computing architectures. This will be complemented by horizontal interoperability across major molecular simulation codes, providing a consistent foundation for integrating workflow managers and ensuring that data generated within the community adheres to agreed FAIR principles. Together, these developments will position CCP5 to continue serving as the central hub for the UK's world-leading activities in functional and advanced materials design through molecular simulation.

More Information

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The Materials Chemistry Consortium (MCC)

Over the next five to ten years, the MCC community will prepare materials modelling software for future computing platforms, vital for the development of Net Zero technologies in line with the UK government's plans for a cleaner world by 2050

The Community

mcc.hec.ac.uk

The High-End Computing Materials Chemistry Consortium exploits national and regional high end computing facilities in a broad programme of work modelling and predicting the structures, properties and reactivities of materials. The consortium includes over 100 research groups with over 700 users registered on the UK national supercomputing service ARCHER2, with an emphasis on modelling at the atomic and molecular level but with growing links to models at larger length and time scales.

The Challenges

A number of grand challenges aligned with government priorities that MCC will address via their current research themes as follows:

Computational Catalysis supports the wide-ranging experimental programmes of UK's catalysis, especially the Catalysis Hub and its partners in both universities and industry. The grand challenge in this area is to generate detailed structural and mechanistic information needed for catalysis optimization and design, which is vital for the development of Net Zero technologies including catalytic CO₂ conversion, ammonia synthesis and plasmonic enhanced photocatalysis.

Environmental and Nuclear Materials involve grand challenges around the development of materials to contain toxic and/or radioactive waste, capture greenhouse gases for long-term storage, remove toxins and pollutants from the biosphere. Projects include new materials for circular economy technologies and environmental protection; detection and catalytic remediation procedures for pollutants in air and water systems; CO₂ utilisation; N₂ activation; disposal and/or recycling of hazardous waste materials; and development of sustainable, non-toxic replacements for structural and functional materials.

Soft Matter and Biomaterials underpins the design of soft materials for biological applications. Understanding the superior properties of biological materials will inform the design of soft matter mimics, with applications to the pharmaceutical, drug delivery platforms, bioimaging, food and cosmetic industries.

Materials Discovery develops and applies computational approaches to find new materials with desired functional properties. Such materials include inorganic, organic (e.g. polymers and pharmaceuticals) and hybrid organic-inorganic (e.g. metal organic frameworks). The development of advanced materials is essential to growth industries including clean energy solutions and quantum technologies.

Energy Materials Modelling involves the grand challenge of battery design, including materials for high energy density cathodes, solid-state batteries and next-generation sodium-ion batteries, interacting with experimental work at the Faraday Institution (FI) and its partners in industry. Nuclear waste storage is also a grand challenge, with work on radiation damage in nuclear materials and materials degradation in partnership with the Nuclear Decommissioning Authority.

Fundamentals of Bulk Materials addresses the morphologies, atomic structure and stability of (poly)crystalline and amorphous phases of bulk materials that underpins almost all themes and assists in a diverse range of applications of materials in technology. It facilitates design and discovery of new materials with tailored properties for energy generation, transport and storage, microelectronics and carbon capture.

Fundamentals of Surfaces and Interfaces bridges method developments and applications in other themes where important processes often occur at poorly characterised interfaces between materials. Grand challenge applications include understanding the role of defects at complex grain boundaries in thin film photovoltaics to expedite optimisation for the fabrication of greener, more efficient materials.

Fundamentals in Low Dimensional Materials seeks to advance our understanding of phenomena that occur when matter is organised at the nanoscale. The predictive challenge is the need to improve our capability to design bias-free methods for evaluating such relationships, with applications including improving solar cell performance by tuning the HOMO-LUMO gap to match frequencies of visible light.

The Solution

To prepare materials modelling software for future computing platforms

To fully realise solutions to the MCC's challenges, we will need to prepare materials modelling software for future computing platforms, which will be increasingly heterogeneous, principally through use of GPUs. This requires a large and sustained effort both within MCC and through participating in related initiatives, e.g. the PAX-HPC project for particle-based simulation methods as part of the UK's ExCALIBUR exascale computing program. **Novel Algorithms for Materials Modelling** are also required and form a theme within the consortium, cutting across application-specific domains, and supporting the development and application of new algorithms for the next generation of materials simulation. This includes emerging techniques to improve on the scope, accuracy and reliability of current materials modelling, together with leveraging developments in quantum computing, machine learning and synergies with other fields e.g., quantum chemistry. Methods beyond the limitations in cost and/or accuracy of DFT, and the materials science specific potential of algorithms designed to exploit emerging quantum computers (via their classical emulation and combination with classical resources) will require much exploration and benchmarking to assess rigorously and objectively their advantages. Large-scale simulation is needed to identify bottlenecks in current techniques and quantify the potential accuracy and range of applicability in these emerging alternatives to the field. Allied to this is the need for access to new platforms in the UK as and when they become available, which will be essential for tackling both challenges. The fact that the MCC workload managed to fill ARCHER2 when it eventually arrived demonstrates the demand from the MCC members a few years ago and this should increase.

The Outcome

Access to exascale HPC to keep internationally competitive with their science output

In three to five years from now, MCC will need access to exascale HPC to keep internationally competitive with their science output. We have been involved in the ExCALIBUR project, preparing for exascale HPC, considered quantum computers, and now looking more carefully at how best to employ AI techniques in new workflows suitable for computers like AIRR. Essentially, we aim to achieve as much impact as possible in the field of materials research with the use of national HPC resources we distribute by sharing ideas and good practices, optimising the performance (scientific throughput per CU) of our software, as well as developing and assessing new workflows and software to achieve our aims.

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The United Kingdom Car-Parrinello Consortium (UKCP)

Over the next five to ten years, UKCP will enable reliable, efficient and predictive simulations of a wide range of materials systems critical to many of the UK Government's missions including "Make Britain a Clean Energy Superpower"

The Community

www.ukcp.ac.uk

UKCP is one of the longest-running High-End Computing Consortia in the UK. The member groups develop quantum mechanics-based simulation methods at the cutting edge of science and capability computing. These methods are generally applicable with key areas that include electric battery materials, photovoltaics, additive manufacturing, and pharmaceutical design. UKCP leads the development of three UK materials modelling packages and contributes to three others, with dozens of community tools across chemistry, physics, engineering and materials sciences. One of the UK apps supported by the consortium, CASTEP, has over 2000 licensed academic research groups and 1000 industrial sites, across 90 countries. The users of these simulation apps include many experimental research scientists, who use the tools to analyse and interpret experimental data and design new experiments. UK national facilities routinely use UKCP developed software, such as Diamond Light Source, ISIS Neutron and Muon Source, and UK High-Field Solid-State NMR Facility. The large global userbase has been made possible only by sustained investment in research software engineering (RSE) over three decades, which has led to software which is capable of advanced quantum mechanical materials simulations. This software can be run efficiently on machines from laptops to supercomputers, with user-friendly interfaces that enable effective use by non-computational specialists.

The Challenge

Deliver effective simulations for materials research with efficient use of future computing capabilities

The methods and software developed by UKCP are applicable to all four themes of the government's industrial strategy. The challenge is to remain at the forefront of state-of-the-art materials simulation while also making the best use of the computational resources available now and in the future. It is essential to incorporate emerging and fast-moving technologies such as quantum computing and AI in the methods and workflows of the community. New methods, technology and techniques offer the challenge of whole-device simulation, combining software across UK communities, to enable rapid advancement of product design and manufacturing processes.

The Solution

Develop new methods to improve materials software, leverage emerging technology and deliver training

Over the next decade UKCP will:

- Develop advanced new methods and techniques to improve the usability, accuracy and performance of materials software, to extend its scientific capabilities to model new experimental properties.
- Derive and implement rare-event sampling methods, multiscale and multiphysics models, and techniques to model dynamics and disorder in complex systems.
- Work with hardware and software vendors to co-design solutions to the technical challenges faced in materials modelling software development.
- Transform our software modelling tools' performance, by developing new algorithms and using both hardware (e.g. GPUs) and software (AI) acceleration.
- Address the AI and Digital Skills gap: Partner with other consortia and computing facilities to devise and deliver training to support both RSEs and scientific researchers, and “Break Down Barriers to Opportunity” by supporting and encouraging currently under-represented groups.

The Outcome

Guide experimental design, expand time scales of materials simulations and train and nurture next generation of users and developers

UKCP will enable world-leading experimental scientists to guide experiment design, interpret, and even predict results, without the need for them to become computational specialists. They will expand the length- and time-scales of materials simulations by several orders of magnitude, and train and nurture the next generation of expert users and developers. This work will enable reliable, efficient, predictive simulations of a wide range of materials systems, including the discovery and design of new materials for battery electrodes and electrolytes, superconductors, magnetic data storage, medical implants and fusion reactor coolant and containment walls. Their roadmap will: maintain and extend the UK's world-leading research in materials modelling; support a wide range of experimental and computational research and researchers across many disciplines, including physics, chemistry, materials science, engineering, earth sciences and life sciences; enable strategically important work in clean energy, sustainable development and future healthcare; and enhance the digital skills of early-career researchers and the next generation UK workforce.

More Information

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The Collaborative Computational Project for NMR Crystallography (CCP-NC)

Over the next 5-10 years CCP-NC aims to leverage the power of modern computational chemistry to facilitate materials characterisation and discovery using NMR to produce a reproducible ecosystem enabling non-experts to apply NMR crystallographic methods to complex materials.

The Community

www.ccpnc.ac.uk

CCP-NC was established in 2010 to support researchers using nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) to understand and characterise materials. This community increasingly relies on computational methods (particularly electronic structure codes) to connect structural models with experimental methods, an approach described as “NMR Crystallography”. CCP-NC develops the software tools and provides training to allow a largely experimental community to exploit the power of modern computational chemistry. Through its software and its website resources, CCP-NC is at the forefront of research internationally in this rapidly developing field.

The Challenge

To leverage the power of modern computational chemistry to facilitate materials characterisation and discovery using NMR

The ability to link experimental NMR data with predictions from quantum chemistry calculations has transformed our ability to characterise materials and relate experimental features to three-dimensional structure. Advances in computational chemistry, such as machine learning (and AI more generally) and quantum computing offer the prospects of applying these methods to significantly more complex materials, such as amorphous drugs and energy materials. Simultaneously, these developments make it increasingly difficult for experimental researchers to apply these sophisticated computational tools efficiently and effectively.

The Solution

Equipping experimental researchers with state-of-the-art computational tools

CCP-NC will use its position at the interface of computational chemistry and experimental NMR to provide tools and training for the next generation of materials researchers, both in academia and industry. Working with developers of quantum chemistry codes, we develop protocols and workflows to ensure that calculations are both robust (delivering trustworthy results) and efficient (using computing resources with maximum energetic efficiency). Building on our existing work on standard file formats and databases of calculation results, we develop tools and working practices to ensure that results are FAIR-ly available and reusable by AI-enabled researchers. By providing a variety of training activities and web resources, we will ensure that best practice is disseminated effectively, to both established and new researchers.

The Outcome

An accessible, reproducible ecosystem enabling non-experts to apply NMR crystallographic methods to complex materials

A coordinated suite of interoperable computational tools, workflows and training resources will be delivered by 2030, enabling experimental and computational researchers to apply NMR crystallographic methods routinely and reproducibly to complex and disordered materials. Integrated, end-to-end workflows will link experimental NMR data with predictions from quantum chemistry, incorporating machine-learning and AI-enabled methods to accelerate structure generation, ensemble exploration, spectral simulation and quantitative comparison. These workflows will deliver robust, trustworthy results while making efficient use of GPU-enabled Tier-1 and Tier-2 high-performance computing resources, preserving methodological transparency and lowering barriers to adoption by non-specialists.

These capabilities will be complemented by community-endorsed protocols for provenance tracking, spectral benchmarking and FAIR data deposition, ensuring that computational results are reusable for data-driven and AI-enabled research. Together, these developments will establish CCP-NC as the UK hub for NMR crystallography and the computational–experimental study of structurally complex materials, strengthening links with crystallography, structure prediction and materials informatics, and supporting long-term UK leadership in materials science.

More Information

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Imaging

The Collaborative Computational Project in Tomographic Imaging (CCPi)

The CCPi Grand Challenge aims to transform X-ray CT from an inspection tool into a quantitative platform for research and industrial verification. It focuses on scaling advanced techniques like hyperspectral and in-situ CT for high-throughput, real-time analysis, integrating multimodal imaging (e.g., neutron, muon, SAR)

The Community

www.ccp.ac.uk

The Collaborative Computational Project in Tomographic Imaging (CCPi) supports the UK non-clinical computed tomography (CT) community by delivering open-source software and expert training to enable researchers to extract higher-quality results from CT data.

In 2018 CCPi helped shape the [EPSRC X-Ray Roadmap](#), which identified key priorities for advancing the field. These included lowering barriers to entry for new users—both in terms of hardware and software—providing training across all experience levels and enabling scientific progress through improvements in temporal and spatial resolution. The roadmap also highlighted the need for new imaging modalities, such as phase contrast, spectral (colour) imaging, and crystallography, as well as the development of advanced in-situ and in-operando techniques.

Since then, CCPi has delivered the Core Imaging Library (CIL) for processing and reconstruction across lab and synchrotron sources; including tools for standard, in-situ and hyperspectral CT. CCPi has provided extensive training through conferences, user meetings and online resources. A new user survey will be made in 2025/26 to ensure that X-ray CT software developments align with the emerging needs through the updating of the CT Roadmap.

The Challenge

Tackling an increasing volume of image datasets and sub-optimal data, leveraging AI and encapsulating Rich Tomography

CT is an invaluable tool for nondestructive testing widely used in industry; it enables both structural and chemical measurements and allows the study of materials properties in situ. Hyperspectral and insitu CT have already been demonstrated at research scale, but the grand challenge lies in deploying these capabilities at industrial scale with high throughput and reliability. Its evolution toward hyperspectral,

highspeed, and multimodal capabilities will be critical for addressing global challenges in energy, sustainability, and resilience.

For **energy solutions**, CT must track structural and chemical changes in working batteries capturing phase evolution, porosity, and catalyst distribution under realistic conditions. These insights are vital for improving materials, durability, and scalable manufacturing to meet netzero goals.

In **harsh environments** such as fusion reactors, advanced engines, and nuclear systems, CT should reveal degradation mechanisms—irradiation, corrosion, embrittlement—under temperature and load, while using spectral contrast to monitor chemistry as coatings and surfaces are engineered for extreme conditions.

For **lowcarbon construction**, CT can quantify hydration, microcracking, carbonation, and recyclability in next generation cements, providing feedback to cut emissions and enable circularity.

Across all domains, CT must evolve to deliver high-throughput workflows, integrate multimodal data and ensure reproducible analytics so that massive 4D datasets become actionable insights for process optimization and real-time decision-making in manufacturing and production environments.

Future imaging must integrate multimodal approaches—combining with other sources such as neutron, muons, emission imaging, Synthetic Aperture Radiography (SAR), , and other techniques with—to address scenarios where X-rays cannot penetrate or full rotation is impossible. The challenge is to develop unified workflows and reconstruction algorithms that fuse sparse, physics-limited data into coherent, quantitative models. This integration will enable imaging of large, dense, or hazardous objects such as nuclear waste, aerospace components, and critical infrastructure, providing actionable insights for design validation, safety assurance, and production quality control in extreme environments.

The Solution

A vast suite of transformative tools, solutions and techniques that will allow researchers to accelerate tasks and maintain high performance

Software is central to unlocking the next generation of CT capabilities, and CCPi will lead by:

- Developing advanced processing pipelines for hyperspectral, in-situ, and multi-modal CT, enabling researchers and industry to extract quantitative structural and chemical information under realistic operating conditions.
- Optimizing performance for scale, creating algorithms and workflows that handle datasets efficiently
- Training the next generation of CT practitioners, ensuring skills in advanced imaging, data analytics, and AI-driven interpretation to support industrial adoption.
- Building reproducible, automated workflows that transform CT from a research tool into a production-ready platform for process optimization, predictive maintenance, and digital twin integration.

The Outcome

A quantitative platform for research and industrial verification

CT will evolve from a powerful inspection tool into a **quantitative platform for research and industrial verification**. It will provide both structural and chemical information in real time, enabling scientists to study materials under realistic conditions and engineers to validate components with greater confidence. High-speed, multi-modal CT will support **faster development cycles**, reduce defects, and improve reliability in manufacturing. This will accelerate innovation in energy technologies, advanced materials, and sustainable construction.

More Information

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The Collaborative Computational Project Synergistic Reconstruction for Biomedical Imaging (CCP SyneRBI)

Over the next five to ten years, CCP SyneRBI develop state-of-the-art open-source software tools and machine learning strategies to translate into higher-performing biomedical scanning software, ultimately improving the quality and longevity of life for people affected by cancer, dementia and other serious illnesses

The Community

www.ccpsynerbi.ac.uk

For medical imaging, the UK is a globally leading country. It has the highest number of medical imaging machines per capita in the world, evenly spread throughout the country. The Collaborative Computational Project in Synergistic Biomedical Imaging (CCP SyneRBI), established in 2015, aims at bringing together the best of the UK's imaging expertise to capitalise on the investment in this area. New research shows that the use of MRI intermediate results can improve Positron Emission Tomography (PET) imaging quality and vice versa, and the latest scanners can acquire Magnetic Resonance (MR) and PET data simultaneously. CCP SyneRBI is dedicated to exploiting exciting new capabilities that the synergy of MR, PET and other imaging modalities can deliver. The main deliverable of the project is an open-source reconstruction software framework named SIRF (Synergistic Image Reconstruction Framework). SIRF is simple enough to use for educational and research purposes, thus reducing the "barrier for entry" for new contributors to imaging research and development, and at the same time powerful enough to process real scanner data.

The Challenge

Improving imaging quality to detect early stages of disease or treatment response as changes are difficult to detect or identify

While tremendous progress has been made in diagnosis and treatment of disease, there is a continuing need to improve early detection, identify correct treatment pathways and monitor advanced therapies. Early diagnostics of cancer saves lives and ameliorates the quality of life for patients with dementia and their families. Medical scanners can exploit different physics and biological properties, leading to different imaging modalities such as PET, Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI) and x-ray Computed Tomography (CT), each with their own properties and advantages. Medical imaging is increasingly used to help clinicians make the correct decisions. Clinical trials of new therapeutics increasingly use imaging for assessing effectiveness and side effects. However, early stages of disease or treatment response are very difficult to identify since

changes can be very small and hard to detect and quantify. This makes any improvement in the quality of imaging produced by medical scanners truly invaluable.

There is a continuous push towards more efficient medical examinations and while there is continuing research to improve scanner hardware, nowadays the biggest innovations come from novel data processing methods, with considerable expertise available in the UK. For instance, research has shown that the use of MRI images can improve PET image quality, and vice versa, with promising results of extending these techniques to other cases, such as using for Molecular Radio Therapy (MRT), a rapidly growing alternative cancer treatment. In addition, there is considerable potential for AI and machine learning to deliver high quality images in challenging conditions. However, the image reconstruction software supplied by the vendors is often proprietary, which prevents researchers to investigate and improve the underlying methods. Current research therefore mostly concentrates on using machine learning on reconstructed images. This presents challenges due to confounding factors introduced by vendor- and site-specific image reconstruction.

These could be reduced by using harmonised image reconstruction methods, but this requires software capable of handling data from various scanners/vendors. Even more powerful is to apply machine learning directly to the measured data from different imaging modalities and integrating it in the image reconstruction process, as this is likely to reduce the risk of hallucinations as well as increase diagnostic sensitivity. Unfortunately, the barrier of entry for researchers from other disciplines (e.g. computer science) to fully exploit multi-modal/multi-vendor data is very high, as it requires detailed knowledge of relevant physics, scanner models, data formats, etc. In addition, it is difficult for bio-medical researchers to remain abreast of the continuous innovation in scanner hardware, preventing current state-of-the-art approaches to be applied in clinical practice and benefitting patients. A further challenge for researchers is that developing and testing such novel methods needs access to large datasets, pooled from several centres.

The Solution

Explore potential of using AI and machine learning, developing flexible open-source software tools for different imaging modalities

CCP SyneRBI brings together the bio-medical research community to enable research into, and translation of, advanced methods in processing methods of multi-modality data, exploiting AI and machine learning strategies. We are developing flexible and fast open-source software tools combining capabilities for different imaging modalities as well as machine learning strategies. The software tools are designed to be simple enough in use for research and teaching purposes and, at the same time, powerful enough to handle real scanner data efficiently. The immediate impact of the software we develop is a much lower “barrier for entry” for new contributors to bio-medical imaging research and development, and the dramatic reduction in time a researcher would spend on the coding - from months to days. This should accelerate the progress in the development of efficient image reconstruction and processing algorithms and foster multi-disciplinary

research. In addition, this allows start-up companies to bring their novel devices to market much faster and cheaper.

The Outcome

State-of-the-art quality scanning software that enables better quality and longevity of life for people affected by serious illness

The open-source software model will allow incorporating contributions from researchers world-wide, with automated and manual checks on software quality. Together with research in exploiting the latest computing hardware, this will ensure long term sustainability. In addition to developing high quality software tools, CCP-SyneRBI are working with UK and international academics to establish standards for raw data, acquisition protocols, data storage and processing methods, as well as enabling automated processing pipelines for processing large and heterogeneous data-sets, ultimately integrated into large data infrastructure projects. These steps should translate into higher quality of bio-medical imaging scanners' software and, eventually - and most importantly - to better quality and longevity of life for people affected by cancer, dementia and other serious illnesses.

More Information

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Astrophysics

Numerical Relativity in the UK (UKNR)

Over the next five to ten years, UKNR will maintain and extend the UK's scientific leadership in gravitational wave science and support the UK's Science and Technology Framework by building the necessary software infrastructure to keep pace in a rapidly changing world

The Community

www.uknumericalrelativity.org

Numerical Relativity (NR) refers to the solution of Einstein's equations on a computer, and ranges from simple laptop calculations in spherical symmetry, to large-scale simulations that require several million core hours each. Simulations of orbits and the merger of black holes and neutron stars have played a central role in the breakthrough results in gravitational-wave astronomy over the last decade, including the dynamics of exotic objects and spacetimes and new areas of exploration in fundamental physics beyond general relativity. UKNR's vision is to bring together all NR groups within the UK to form a collaborative community with a shared vision and speaks with one voice. This community will be both inward looking and outward looking. For the former, UKNR will foster collaboration in code development/exploitation with code sharing and training and identify the UK's future digital infrastructure needs as a community. UKNR will survey the current and future global digital infrastructure landscape to formulate a UK-wide strategic plan for NR code development as they move into the exascale era.

The Challenge

Increasing the precision of numerical output to keep up with Big Data and development of new techniques that work beyond Einstein's theory

The detection of gravitational waves 10 years ago by the Laser Interferometer Gravitational Observatory (LIGO) heralded a golden age of gravitational wave physics, allowing us to probe hitherto unreachable regimes of fundamental physics such as the nature of gravity, black holes and the origins of the Big Bang. To make these discoveries requires precise theoretical predictions, but since the Einstein equations are famously intractable analytically, NR is key to solving the Einstein equations and making theoretical predictions. As major participants in many international multi-billion-pound experiments with a legacy of gravitational breakthroughs, and scientific leadership in numerical relativity, the UK plays key roles in this worldwide endeavour to understand the nature of our universe. There are two major scientific challenges in numerical relativity today: increasing the precision of numerical output to keep up with the inevitable deluge of high precision data from future detectors, and the development of new methodologies to compute predictions of fundamental physics beyond Einstein's theory. To meet these challenges requires significant breakthroughs in the development of computational techniques and compute infrastructure.

A major strength of UKNR is its scientific nimbleness, responding quickly and decisively to the rapidly changing digital infrastructure landscape and constantly shifting scientific frontiers. UKNR code developers led the international NR community in transitioning from CPUs to GPUs and pioneered the first codes to probe theories beyond Einstein's and other new physics. In parallel, we have played a key role in developing the flagship waveform models that have been used in all LIGO-Virgo-KAGRA observations to date. As the international scientific community braces itself for a momentous few decades of discoveries with gravitational wave astronomy, maintaining and extending this scientific

lead is key to ensure that UK science remains at the forefront. Beyond the scientific challenges outlined in the UK Compute Roadmap, creating a sovereign digital infrastructure is key to remain resilient in the face of global instability. While scientific computing often relies on open-source libraries, many of these libraries were developed in non-UK national labs. The NR community is no different as almost all their codes rely on extensive libraries that they do not fully control. Finally, and perhaps most importantly, the dizzying rise of AI has significant implications across all scientific disciplines, and NR will be no exception. While standard neural networks have been applied in data analysis in astrophysics for many years, its use in NR is nascent. This provides a huge opportunity for UKNR scientists to assume leadership in this field.

The Solution

Achieving high precision with less, integrating AI and machine learning methodologies into NR and achieving software sovereignty

Over the next decade, UKNR aims to maintain and extend their international lead in the development of cutting-edge numerical relativity codes, building on three interconnected principles: achieving high precision with less, integrating AI and machine learning methodologies into numerical relativity and achieving software sovereignty.

Achieving high precision with less: UKNR will reach the required precision for the next generation gravitational wave detectors by adopting more energy efficient technologies (e.g. our recent transition from CPUs into GPUs), seeking efficiency gains from refining present computational methodologies (such as factoring codes to take advantage of much lower energy single precision compute units), and building completely new numerical methodologies such as the Physics-Informed Neural Networks (PINN) to allow upscaling of low resolution simulations.

Incorporating AI and machine learning into numerical relativity: UKNR will leverage the rapid advances of AI and machine learning techniques to achieve precision goals, solve presently intractable scientific problems, and improve their code development workflow. However, achieving consistency, reliability and explainability is a key requirement for any successful integration of AI into numerical relativity. UKNR intend to collaborate with AI and machine learning experts to achieve this goal.

Achieving software sovereignty: In an increasingly uncertain world, it is crucial that the UK achieves digital sovereignty. In particular, the UK needs to be at the forefront of code development, steering the direction of research, and becoming independent of hardware developments -- a goal that aligns with EU initiatives around homegrown hardware from the ARM and RISC-V ecosystem. In the context of NR where many codes still rely on non-UK compute libraries (e.g. the US ECP-based AMReX), UKNR plan to build a UK base capability to develop our own compute libraries for adaptive mesh finite difference solvers, seeking out collaboration with other CoSeC CCPs which require such technology.

The Outcome

To maintain and extend UK's scientific leadership in the present golden age of gravitational wave science

Over the next 10 years, UKNR aims not only to maintain the UK's scientific leadership in the present golden age of gravitational wave science, but to extend it. It will support the UK's Science and Technology Framework by building the necessary digital software infrastructure and developing the human capital, keeping pace in a rapidly changing world and digital landscape. The coalescing of the UKNR as a community has opened multiple avenues of code sharing and

consolidation, such as the joint use of underlying libraries. This consolidation is a force multiplier within the community. Participating in the CoSeC framework has provided, and will continue to provide, the opportunity to contribute and benefit from cross-cutting knowledge transfer, and the community fully intends to participate in the process to make the UK HPC community more than the sum of its parts.

More Information

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Quantum Computing

Collaborative Computational Project Quantum Computing (CCP-QC)

Over the next five to ten years, CCP-QC will align with the goal of the UK National Quantum Strategy Mission by supporting and developing the commercial provision of quantum computing as a service and their integration into high performance computational workflows, to have accessible quantum computers capable of running 1 trillion operations by 2035

The Community

www.ccp-qc.ac.uk

CCP-QC brings together close co-operation between other CCPs and the quantum computing community, rather than build a separate community for quantum computing. Encompassing members interested in enhancing their simulations by adding quantum computing capability to their code, as well as researchers working on applications of quantum computing to simulations, CCP-QC generates projects and develops methods appropriate to specific applications, leading to proof-of-concept demonstrations on early quantum hardware. They also have a partnership with the National Quantum Computing Centre (NQCC) in developing early applications of quantum computing, providing training and supporting career development. CCP-QC promotes cross-CCP networking to share knowledge on early applications of quantum computing, enabling the widest possible early adoption of quantum enhanced computational science, collaborating with industry and partners who are key players in developing quantum computing technology both in the UK, and internationally.

The Challenge

To support the UK Strategy by demonstrating quantum assisted computation, developing enhanced algorithms and workflows

[The UK National Quantum Strategy Missions](#) set out by government in 2023 lists five missions for quantum technology to deliver over the next ten years. The relevant mission for quantum computing is Mission One: **By 2035, there will be accessible, UK-based quantum computers capable of running 1 trillion operations and supporting applications that provide benefits well in excess of classical supercomputers across key sectors of the economy.** Crucially, this will be achieved not only by supporting commercial provision of quantum computing as a service, but also by seamlessly integrating quantum computing into high performance computational workflows, enabling user access and widespread adoption. High impact will be achieved in the following sectors at a minimum: healthcare, finance, transport, defence, energy, and manufacturing. The missions specify milestones towards the 2035 capability. For Mission One:

- By 2028, extending beyond the NISQ-era with a million quantum operations, which will enable the exploration of applications associated with the simulation of chemical processes, helping to improve catalyst design, for example.
- By 2032, demonstrating large-scale error correction capabilities with a billion quantum operations, with applications including accelerated drug discovery.
- By 2035, achieving quantum advantage at scale through reaching a trillion quantum operations, enabling applications such as optimising the production of clean hydrogen.

Ensuring that scientific advances in quantum computing applications can be applied with confidence in both industry and the public sector requires "real-world engineering utility" - industrial companies running reliable quantum computing to improve their designs. Part of this requires quantum computing to meet any accuracy requirements from regulatory bodies. In much of engineering (especially aerospace and civil/structures) there are strict design regulations, and quantum computing will need to work within legal frameworks and standards. The potential legal barrier of integrating quantum into mainstream engineering compute (e.g. helping to design a plane) has not yet been considered in detail.

The Solution

To enable early adoption of quantum computing in the workflows of CCPs and HECs

The first milestone - useful chemical and materials science calculations assisted by quantum computing - is just two years ahead. Thus, the first grand challenge for CCP-QC is to demonstrate useful quantum assisted computation for a specific industrially-relevant application within the domain of chemistry and materials science. This will require partnership with the relevant CCPs, HECs (CCP5, CCP9 and MCC) and the STFC Compute team, to enable early adoption of quantum computing in the workflows to deliver useful results. Two years from now is very ambitious, but CCP-QC are building on collaborations which began in 2019, with useful algorithms and workflows at their disposal from research funded under the ExCALIBUR programme and the CCP Bridge projects. With further resources, and in collaboration with other players, including the NQCC and QCi3 Quantum Tech Hub, this grand challenge is achievable. The next milestone is just four years after 2028: with larger quantum computers it will be possible to scale up to biomolecules. Collaboration with CCPBioSim will be critical to achieving meaningful, useful results. Alongside this, if CCP-QC are to achieve useful quantum computing enhanced workflows in other application areas besides quantum simulation, they will start working now to develop the algorithms and workflows ready for large scale quantum computers in 2035. The community already have an established collaboration and network for fluid simulations, and some of the methods can be expected to be more widely applicable for differential areas. More general applications have also been developed as part of the ExCALIBUR programme and need to be tested for future deployment as integrated hardware becomes available.

The Outcome

Ensuring that scientific advances in quantum computing applications can be applied with confidence in both industry and the public sector

Ensuring that scientific advances in quantum computing applications can be applied with confidence in both industry and the public sector requires "real-world engineering utility" - industrial companies running reliable quantum computing to improve their designs. Part of this requires quantum computing to meet any accuracy requirements from regulatory bodies. In much of engineering (especially aerospace and civil/structures) there are strict design regulations, and quantum computing will need to work within legal frameworks and standards. The potential legal barrier of integrating quantum into mainstream engineering compute (e.g. helping to design a plane) has not yet been considered in detail.

CCP-QC has already developed quantum accreditation - an efficient classical scheme of determining the correctness of real-world quantum computations. This scheme does not rely on performing an exponentially expensive classical simulation of the relevant quantum computation. NPL is one of their key collaborators and is already working on standards for quantum computing. There is much more to be done beyond their current focus, working with application communities to develop ways to certifying quantum computing efficiently against relevant standards and regulations, and to update regulations where necessary to allow future use of quantum computing.

More Information

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Digital Humanities

The Collaborative Computational Project for Arts, Humanities and Culture (CCP-AHC)

Over the next five to ten years, CCP-AHC will become the first network of its kind to support the AHRC community by developing wide-scale access to AI inference for primary source materials

The Community

Collaborative
Computational Project
for Arts, Humanities
and Culture

www.ccpahc.ac.uk

CCP-AHC will be the first network of its kind to support the AHRC research community and have a significant impact both nationally and internationally. The creation of CCP-AHC is timely, given the proliferation of computational tools and techniques—more specifically HPC and AI - into various research agendas of the AHRC. With the AHRC research community increasingly dependent on all aspects of digital research infrastructure (DRI) and with few collaborative efforts focused on developing cohesive visions, initiatives, or DRI assets, the launch of CCP-AHC is very timely.

The Challenge

Access and available services needed to essential services for AHC researchers

Arts, humanities, and culture (AHC) touch every citizen's life. Research in the area contributes to the national wellbeing, the preservation of the natural and built historic environment, and the maintenance of just and strong institutions. It directly addresses phenomena such as creativity and meaning, by turning to archives for evidence of human behaviour which may be preserved as text, image, sound, video, or artefact. By interpreting these traces of human activity, AHC researchers develop a critical understanding of contemporary challenges such as social cohesion, societal resilience, climate change, responsible innovation, and the preservation of diverse languages and intangible practices. The digital transformation of research enables the use of large-scale computational techniques to support interpretations. The recent rapid development of data-intensive techniques suitable for AHC data, driven by public and private investment in artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning innovation, alongside the consolidation of DRI provision across research areas in the UK offer an opportunity to realise the promise of wider-than-ever availability of the source materials of AHC research.

Galleries, libraries, and museums already hold terabytes of digital collections, countless millions of other holdings, sometimes in personal, local, or community collections, which are yet to be ingested or processed. Existing large-scale born-digital collections, such as the UK Web Archive, are already being curated today at petabyte scale. AHRC-led investments will in the coming decade produce large volumes of digitised holdings

in the coming decade. However, born-digital archiving efforts or the production of new digitisations of analogue material do not by themselves produce new results. These data often need to be further transcribed, annotated, or otherwise reformatted before they can be analysed computationally. Researchers need access to services that allow them to ready them for large-scale processing by specific research codes.

The Solution

To accelerate the production of research in AHC by making established techniques available to technical and non-technical AHC researchers

There is no one-size-fits all code or service that will accelerate the production of research uniformly across the varied subfields within the arts, humanities, and culture area. However, there are many currently labour-intensive operations that shared across many disciplines. These tasks have established computational solutions, approach human-level accuracy, including audio transcription, optical character recognition (OCR), and image captioning. These are all powered by accelerated compute and, in many cases, open-source codes and pre-trained models, which are already competitive with state-of-the-art technology. CCP-AHC's vision is to make these techniques available to technical and non-technical AHC researchers working across academia, the non-profit sector, and the culture industries regardless of their affiliation or current access to compute and ability.

This is made complex by the diversity of kinds of data that support AHC research: texts, images, video, audio, and multi-dimensional data derived from physical artefacts are all routinely used. The rapid development of novel approaches also demands new benchmarks to help researchers find appropriate, efficient, sustainable and responsible solutions. In the future, no AHC researcher or innovator will be prevented from exploring the capabilities of AI and machine learning, running on publicly large-scale compute by the uneven distribution of skilled dRTPs or access to DRI within the sector.

The Outcome

Wide-scale access to AI inference for digitised AHC primary source materials

In the future, no AHC researcher or innovator will be prevented from exploring the capabilities of AI and machine learning, running on publicly large-scale compute by the uneven distribution of skilled dRTPs or access to DRI within the sector.

More Information

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Particle Physics

The Collaborative Computational Project in Theoretical and Experimental Particle Physics (CCP-TEPP)

Over the next five to ten years, CCP-TEPP will develop advanced computational methods to process unprecedented volumes of experimental data and deliver high-precision theoretical predictions. This transformation will enable next-generation particle physics research to uncover new phenomena and make breakthrough discoveries about the fundamental nature of matter and the universe

The Community

Over the next decade, research in theoretical and experimental particle physics (TEPP) will be driven by a tenfold increase in data from facilities such as the High-Luminosity Large Hadron Collider (HL-LHC) and next-generation neutrino experiments. This scale of data and complexity demands a transformation in computational methods: traditional approaches cannot cope with the challenge of processing, simulating, and analyzing these vast datasets at the precision needed to uncover new physics beyond the Standard Model—such as understanding the matter–antimatter asymmetry, probing the Higgs boson in detail, and exploring phenomena that could reshape our view of the universe.

CCP-TEPP builds on the UK’s strong culture of collaboration in TEPP. Its aim is to support researchers across theory and experiment, alongside global academic and industrial partners, in developing and maintaining advanced computational methods and software frameworks. These tools will modernize TEPP workflows for modeling, data processing, and analysis to meet the requirements of next-generation experiments.

The Challenge

To transform computational methods to handle an order-of-magnitude increase in data and complexity from future particle physics experiments and theoretical developments.

The grand challenge for CCP-TEPP is to transform computational methods so they can handle an order-of-magnitude increase in data and complexity from next-generation particle physics experiments, enabling discoveries that redefine our understanding of the universe.

Experiments must process unprecedented data volumes from facilities such as the HL-LHC, neutrino observatories, and dark matter searches—enabling simulation, real-time triggering, filtering, and reconstruction while maintaining accuracy. For theory, the challenge is to produce predictions with the precision required to guide and interpret these experiments, through high-accuracy lattice QCD calculations,

exploration of physics beyond the Standard Model, and simulations of extreme conditions such as the quark-gluon plasma.

Meeting these demands requires a major transformation of computational methods and workflows, integrating advanced algorithms, AI-driven approaches, and exascale computing to achieve the speed, scalability, and precision needed across the entire pipeline. This transformation is essential for the UK to maintain and strengthen its global leadership in uncovering new physics and answering the most profound questions about the universe.

The Solution

To deliver scalable, modular frameworks that exploit HPC, GPU acceleration, and AI-driven enhancements for real-time data processing and high-precision theoretical calculations

Over the next decade, CCP-TEPP will lead the development of next-generation computational frameworks for theoretical and experimental particle physics that combine high-performance computing (HPC), GPU acceleration, and advanced algorithms with emerging AI techniques. These tools will enable researchers to process and analyze the unprecedented data volumes expected from the High-Luminosity LHC and future neutrino experiments in real time, while maintaining the precision required for discovery.

The community will deliver scalable software platforms optimized for modern heterogeneous architectures—multicore CPUs, GPUs, and exascale systems—ensuring particle physics workflows can fully exploit current and future computing resources. AI and machine learning will be integrated strategically, building on TEPP's leadership in these fields, for example to accelerate event selection and simulation, but the foundation will remain robust physics-based algorithms validated against experimental and theoretical benchmarks.

CCP-TEPP will also provide modular frameworks for detector simulation, event generation, and theoretical calculations such as lattice QCD and beyond the Standard Model studies. These frameworks will allow rapid incorporation of new physics models and experimental insights, dramatically reducing analysis timelines and computational costs while improving automation. By combining HPC, GPU acceleration, and AI-driven enhancements, CCP-TEPP will modernize particle physics software, strengthen UK leadership in global collaborations, and train the next generation of researchers in cutting-edge computational science.

The Outcome

To further the UK's leadership in TEPP by creating a next generation of software frameworks for data analysis and theoretical calculations to enable world-leading discoveries.

A modern, scalable computational ecosystem that empowers UK researchers to deliver world-leading breakthroughs in particle physics and advance STFC's strategic vision. CCP-TEPP will underpin discoveries that address the most fundamental questions about matter and the universe, while reinforcing the UK's position as a global leader in international collaborations tackling these challenges.

By integrating HPC, GPU acceleration, and AI-driven enhancements into robust physics-based workflows, CCP-TEPP will also foster partnerships with industry to drive innovation in advanced computing technologies with benefits beyond academia. This combination of scientific leadership, technological innovation, and international collaboration will ensure the UK remains at the forefront of particle physics and computational science, while cultivating a highly skilled workforce in advanced computing and AI integration.

More Information

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